

Operationalizing Workable Human–Wildlife Coexistence in Chitwan National Park, Nepal

Based on PhD research conducted at National Dong Hwa University, Taiwan.
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Submitted by

Dr. Arockia E J Ferdin

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ferdinenv@gmail.com, ferdin90@protonmail.com

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ORCID	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0197-6980
Supervisors	Dr. Lee, C. H. (Taiwan) Dr. Baskaran, N. (India)
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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to

My parents

Einstien and Ramola

*Whose sacrifices and everlasting encouragement helped me pursuit my
dreams.*

“It's surely our responsibility to do everything within our power to create
a planet that provides a home not just for us, but for all life on Earth.”

Sir David Attenborough

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1 General Introduction

1.1 Human–Wildlife Conflict: An Overview

Around the world, *Homo sapiens* have been safeguarding their property and protecting themselves from wild animals for centuries (Treves et al., 2006). Human–wildlife conflict (HWC) has been a problem for as long as humans have lived alongside wildlife (Anand & Radhakrishna, 2017). The earliest known evidence of humans being preyed upon by animals is the discovery of a hominid child's skull, killed by a leopard's lethal attack dating back one million years (Kruuk, 2002). The advent of agricultural practices and livestock keeping, approximately 10,000 years ago, marked the onset of crop raiding and livestock depredation incidents (Gordon, 2009). While HWC has a long historical presence, at present HWC is a global issue (Lischka et al., 2020; Madden, 2004), that has a significant environmental challenge to human society and has serious consequences for both wildlife and humans (Anand & Radhakrishna, 2017). HWC is a significant barrier to achieving sustainable development (Su et al., 2022).

According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature Species Survival Commission, HWC is defined as “struggles that emerge when the presence or behaviour of wildlife poses actual or perceived, direct and recurring threat to human interests or needs, leading to disagreements between groups of people and negative impacts on people and/or wildlife” (IUCN SSC HWCTF, 2020). HWC is increasing in frequency and severity, posing a growing threat to the survival of many endangered species worldwide. There are no signs of this trend slowing down, and it is likely to continue (Distefano, 2005; Madden, 2004). HWC occurs when the needs and behaviour of wildlife overlap with the goals of humans, or when the goals of humans overlap with the needs of wildlife (Distefano, 2005; Madden, 2004). This can lead to negative interactions between humans and wildlife (Conover, 2001).

From a human-centred perspective, HWC can occur when wildlife intentionally or unintentionally damage crops, injure or kill livestock, or threaten the safety of people or harm people (König et al., 2020; Lute et al., 2018). HWCs are widespread in both developing and developed countries (Manfredo & Dayer, 2004). It occurs frequently in both rural and urban settings, including agricultural landscapes, urban areas, peri-urban regions, and near protected areas (PAs) (König et al., 2020; Manfredo & Dayer, 2004). Due to this it is receiving increasing attention from conservation biologists, ecologists, and wildlife managers worldwide (Dickman, 2010; Messmer, 2000; Peterson et al., 2010; Wieczorek Hudenko, 2012).

As cultivation and human development encroach upon PAs, these areas are transforming into isolated pockets of natural habitat, leading to competition between wildlife and humans for space, resources, and habitat (Madden, 2004). The specific circumstances of each conflict or coexistence situation are unique, due to a variety of factors, including the biological, geographic, political, economic, social, institutional, financial, cultural, and historical features of the situation (Madden, 2004). HWC intensifies when local people that share landscape with wildlife perceive that wildlife's needs or interests are prioritized over their own, or when local institutions and people are not able to effectively manage the conflict (Madden, 2004).

The fear of being attacked and killed by a large carnivorous or herbivorous wildlife stands as a significant underlying factor in many cases of HWCs (Thirgood et al., 2005). HWCs also can have negative impacts on people's well-being, including their physical and mental health, safety, and economic security (Distefano, 2005). In addition to apparent consequences, HWCs also has hidden costs which are widespread and poorly documented in developing countries (Barua et al., 2013).

The conservation of problematic wildlife responsible for crop raiding, livestock depredation, and posing threats to human safety presents a complex issue for policymakers and wildlife managers (Madden, 2004; Messmer, 2000; Thirgood et al., 2005). The common response to these costs involves resorting to lethal control methods (Dickman, 2010). As people around the world work to find ways to live alongside wildlife, there is growing interest in non-lethal solutions to HWC. This includes raising human tolerance for wildlife and developing non-lethal management techniques (Treves et al., 2006). If park management does not adequately address conflicts with HWC-affected communities, those communities may become angry and resentful, which could hinder conservation efforts (Madden, 2004; Woodroffe et al., 2005).

HWC can result in negative consequences across social, ecological, and economic dimensions. Surprisingly, policymakers tend to neglect this critical issue, despite its far-reaching implications (Gross et al., 2021). Collectively, there is a growing recognition that involving local communities in decision-making regarding conservation policies is crucial for the long-term sustainable management of PAs, especially when these decisions impact the economic or social well-being of the local communities (Dickman, 2010; Hulme & Murphree, 2001).

1.2 Trouble in paradise

Nepal, a mountainous and landlocked country situated in the central Himalayas between two mega-diverse nations, India and China, covers only a small fraction of the

world's landmass, representing less than 0.1%. Despite its relatively modest size, Nepal boasts an exceptional range of diverse habitats and a wealth of biodiversity within its borders (Paudel et al., 2012). Nepal possesses a unique biogeographic profile, characterized by a wide range of altitudes, spanning from 70 to 8,848 meters, and a diverse array of climatic conditions. As a result, Nepal contributes significantly to global biodiversity, accounting for 3.2% of the world's flora and 1.1% of its fauna (NTNC, 2020; Paudel et al., 2012).

Nepal has designated a total of twenty protected areas, comprising twelve national parks, six conservation areas, one wildlife reserve, and one hunting reserve. Additionally, there are thirteen buffer zones associated with these PAs, collectively covering 23.39% of the country's land (DNPWC, 2022). These PAs encompass a wide range of landscapes, from the alluvial tall grasslands and tropical forests found in the lowland Terai regions to the rugged, snow-covered mountains, and dry rangelands found in the high mountain regions (DNPWC, 2022). Six out of ten Ramsar sites, internationally significant wetlands, are situated within PAs, and approximately 18% of the nation's entire forested land is located within these designated areas (DNPWC, 2022).

Many of Nepal's PAs have been established with a primary focus on the conservation of large mammals (Baral, Sharma, Rimal, et al., 2021). The Department of National Parks and Wildlife Conservation (DNPWC) has made remarkable strides in protecting wildlife with notable achievements including the revival of threatened species such as the Royal Bengal tiger (*Panthera tigris tigris*), the great Indian rhinoceros (*Rhinoceros unicornis*), the Indian elephant (*Elephas maximus indicus*), Indian antelope (*Antelope cervicapra*), swamp deer (*Rucervus duvaucelii*), wild water buffaloes (*Bubalus arnee*), and gharials (*Gavialis gangeticus*) from the brink of extinction (DNPWC, 2022). However, the rise in populations of these threatened species, including elephants, rhinos, tigers and the Indian leopard (*Panthera pardus fusca*) has led to an increase in HWC since the inception and enforcement of these PAs (Acharya et al., 2016; Bhattarai et al., 2019; CNP, 2018; Lamichhane et al., 2019a; Pant et al., 2023).

HWC is on the rise in both frequency and severity across Nepal (Acharya et al., 2017; Karki et al., 2022). Approximately two-thirds of Nepal's population relies on agriculture as their primary means of livelihood (Seoraj-Pillai & Pillay, 2017). Communities residing near PAs in the country face heightened vulnerability, particularly regarding their financial well-being. In cases where PA management fails to adequately protect these areas, residents sometimes resort to encroaching on the land (Dahal et al., 2022). The most prevalent and significant types of HWC involve crop damage, livestock loss, property destruction, harm or injury to humans caused by wildlife, and, conversely, retaliatory killing of problematic wildlife and habitat degradation inflicted by humans

(Acharya et al., 2017; CNP, 2018; Lamichhane et al., 2018). Furthermore, HWC incidents also occur when people enter core areas in search of fodder, firewood, and fish (Dahal et al., 2022).

The Community Forests Programme (CFP) was initially launched in 1978 to transfer government-owned land to local communities, enabling the local and sustainable management of forests and resources (Acharya, 2002; Baral, Sharma, Kunwar, et al., 2021). About 40% of the forest areas outside the PAs have been managed through the BZCF programme in Nepal (Acharya et al., 2016). The CFP offered substantial benefits to the local community when the collection of forest products from the core zone of PA was prohibited (Thing & Poudel, 2017). The successful implementation of CFP has contributed to the restoration of degraded forests, enabling wildlife to venture closer to human settlements. Consequently, this has led to an increased frequency of local encounters between people and wildlife, exacerbating HWC in Nepal (Anup et al., 2018; Baral, Sharma, Rimal, et al., 2021).

The population of rhinos has grown from about 100 individuals in the early 1960s to 752 in 2021. The tiger population has also seen an increase, rising from 121 individuals in 2009 to 355 in 2022. Furthermore, the elephant population has surged from approximately 50 individuals in the 1990s to 227 in 2020 (DNPWC, 2022). The heightened competition among wildlife within PAs, coupled with the increase in human population, illegal encroachment, and habitat fragmentation, as well as the presence of agricultural fields creating new habitats in human-dominated landscapes, results in more frequent occurrences of conflicts (Acharya et al., 2017; Bhattarai, 2001; Gross et al., 2021).

In Nepal, the majority of wildlife-related damages go unreported, making it unclear to what extent such damage occurs (DNPWC, 2017). However, between 2000 and 2020, Nepal documented approximately 1,139 fatalities among large mammals and 887 human casualties (Baral et al., 2022). Among wildlife casualties, leopards accounted for the highest losses, followed by rhinos, tigers, and elephants. Conversely, leopards were responsible for the highest human casualties, followed by elephants, tigers, and rhinos. Furthermore, Nepal reported nearly 800 cases of crop depredation by Asian elephants (517 cases) and rhinos (280 cases), along with 357 instances of livestock depredation by tigers (77 cases) and leopards (280 cases) annually (Baral et al., 2022).

1.3 The case of Chitwan National Park

Chitwan National Park (Chitwan NP), the first iconic National Park in south-central Nepal is not an exception to HWCs (CNP, 2018; Sharma, 1990). The reserve houses a substantial population of mega-herbivores, including Asian elephants and the great

Indian rhinoceros, as well as large carnivores like the Royal Bengal tiger and Asiatic leopards (Karki et al., 2015; Subedi et al., 2013). Conservation efforts, such as participatory programs and habitat restoration in buffer zone community forests (BZFC), coupled with strict protection measures enforced by the Nepalese Army in the core area, have gradually led to an increase in the populations of mega-carnivores and mega-herbivores within the park (Karki et al., 2015; Lamichhane et al., 2018; Subedi et al., 2013). Consequently, HWC has emerged as a significant challenge in fostering harmonious coexistence in Chitwan NP (CNP, 2018). For example, between 1998 and 2016, the park experienced a total of 4,104 reported HWC incidents, encompassing 2,213 cases of livestock depredation, 651 instances of crop depredation, 564 human injuries, 418 incidents of property damage, and 168 human casualties (Lamichhane et al., 2018).

Recognizing the severity of the situation, the park management introduced several initiatives to enhance the tolerance of local communities toward wildlife and to foster a positive park-people relationship. The park allocates 30% to 50% of its revenue to the respective Buffer Zone for conservation initiatives, community development and Buffer Zone Community Forest management (CNP, 2018; Jones, 2007). There are 22 Buffer Zone User Committees (BZUC) in the park. The BZUCs are major stakeholders, and they are responsible for designing and implementing buffer zone programs. They act as a liaison between park and local community and assist in relief payment for the wildlife victims (CNP, 2018; Lamichhane et al., 2019b). The revenue provided by the park accounted for over 50% of the BZUC budget (Lamichhane et al., 2019b). The BZUCs primarily allocated their funds to construct and maintain physical barriers, including electrical, barbed wire, mesh wire, and plain cement concrete fences with mesh wire, as measures to mitigate conflicts (Lamichhane et al., 2019b).

A relief payment program was initiated to assist wildlife victims in covering partial losses. Over an 18-year period, from 1998 to 2016, claimants received a total of approximately USD 403,000 (Lamichhane et al., 2019b). The majority of these relief payments were provided for human death (54%), followed by human injuries (21.5%), livestock losses (13.8%), crop depredation (7.1%), and property losses (3.5%) (Lamichhane et al., 2019b). In 2009, the relief payment for human casualties was increased to USD 7,500 per person (CNP, 2018). The community based anti-poaching unit and rapid response teams were established for anti-poaching and assist the wildlife victims involving the local communities (CNP, 2018). The park stands as one of Nepal's highly visited tourist places, and the BZCFs also participate in wildlife tourism, thereby generating extra income for the local community (CNP, 2018).

1.4 Rationale of the study

Despite years of implementing conflict mitigation strategies, community engagement, and numerous research investigations, HWC continues to persist as a significant and complex challenge, posing a significant threat to both wildlife and local communities in the park (CNP, 2018; DNPWC, 2022). While the park management has made considerable strides toward coexistence in the human-dominated landscape, local communities continue to grapple with HWC, enduring human casualties, property damage, and crop and livestock depredation (CNP, 2018; DNPWC, 2022).

While wildlife in the park adapts to the human-modified landscape, local communities also possess the capacity to adapt to the presence of wildlife in their surroundings (Carter & Linnell, 2023). Recognizing the increasing importance of involving local communities in decision-making processes (Dickman, 2010; Hulme & Murphree, 2001), identifying community-preferred coexistence strategies, and understanding their perceptions regarding the importance and effectiveness of HWC management strategies are essential steps in designing effective, long-term HWC management strategies and achieving workable coexistence in Chitwan NP. Furthermore, understanding the trade-offs residents are willing to make between different coexistence strategies — and how these preferences vary across demographic groups — is critical for designing preference-informed, adaptive management interventions.

1.5 Research objectives and research questions

This study aims to explore community-preferred coexistence strategies and gain insight into the local community's perceptions of the importance and effectiveness of HWC management strategies in Chitwan NP with the following objectives.

1.5.1 Study objectives

This thesis is grounded in two empirical studies conducted in the buffer zone of the park, Nepal, each contributing a distinct but complementary perspective on human-wildlife coexistence. Together, they address the gap in understanding how local communities perceive, evaluate, and prefer strategies for managing HWC in a biodiversity-rich, human-dominated landscape.

The first study (Ferdin et al., 2024) applies Importance-Performance Analysis (IPA) to evaluate community perspectives on HWC management strategies in the park. It seeks to assess not only what strategies communities consider important, but also how well those strategies are perceived to be performing — thereby enabling park managers to prioritize interventions based on stakeholder-informed evidence. Specifically, this

study pursues three objectives: (i) to identify HWC management strategies considered important to communities living in the buffer zone; (ii) to explore variations in the perceived importance and performance of these strategies between farmers and non-farmers; and (iii) to determine how these perceptions vary across the four administrative sectors of the park.

The second study (Ferdin et al., 2025) adopts a forward-looking approach, using a discrete choice experiment to understand buffer zone residents' preferences for strategies that enhance their adaptive capacity to coexist with wildlife. Grounded in adaptive capacity theory, this study addresses two research questions: (i) what are residents' overall preferences for strategies that enhance their adaptive capacity to coexist with wildlife?; and (ii) which demographic groups are more likely to prefer those strategies? By examining how residents evaluate trade-offs between different coexistence strategies, this study yields policy-relevant insights that better align management decisions with local community preferences, with particular attention to indigenous communities given their cultural and conservation significance in Chitwan NP.

Together, the two studies pursue the overarching objective of this thesis: to explore community-preferred coexistence strategies and gain insight into local communities' perceptions of the importance and effectiveness of HWC management strategies in Chitwan NP, thereby informing the design of effective, long-term, and community-inclusive HWC management approaches.

1.6 Thesis structure

This thesis is organized into five chapters. **Chapter 1** provides a general introduction, outlining the global and national context of HWC, the specific challenges faced in Chitwan NP, the rationale for this study, and the research objectives. **Chapter 2** describes the study area, presenting the historical, ecological, and socio-demographic context of Chitwan NP and its buffer zone communities. **Chapter 3** presents the first empirical study (Ferdin et al., 2024), to evaluate community perceptions of the importance and effectiveness of HWC management strategies across the four administrative sectors of the park. **Chapter 4** presents the second empirical study (Ferdin et al., 2025), grounded in adaptive capacity theory to understand buffer zone residents' preferences for coexistence strategies. **Chapter 5** provides a general discussion and conclusion, synthesizing the key findings of both studies, discussing their implications for HWC management in Chitwan NP, and offering recommendations for policy and future research.

2 Study Area

2.1 Park's historical perspective

Prior to 1950s, the forest in the Chitwan Valley was safeguarded by Rana rulers, who designated it as a hunting ground for themselves and their esteemed guests, which included the royalties from Europe (mostly from the East India Company) and the Princely states of India (CNP, 2018; Whalley, 1981). Although these great hunting parties were organized at infrequent intervals, they resulted in the significant killing of iconic game animals (Whalley, 1981). According to the records, a single great hunting party was responsible for killing a staggering number of wild animals, including 120 tigers, 38 rhinos, 27 leopards, and 15 bears. This event illustrates the abundance of wildlife present in Chitwan Valley's lush forests at that time (CNP, 2018). The *Tharu* people were the only inhabitants of Chitwan Valley until the 1950s. They practiced shifting cultivation and relied on forest products for their livelihoods and their resistance to malaria allowed them to survive in the region (Müller-Böker, 1991; Whalley, 1981).

Following the overthrow of the Rana regime in 1951, the dire conditions faced by hill people led to a mass exodus to the lowlands (Tarai) in search of new arable land (Gurung, 1983; Whalley, 1981). Coinciding with this, a comprehensive malaria eradication initiative and a resettlement program were initiated to alleviate population pressure in the hills (Gurung, 1983; Whalley, 1981). The lowlands of Chitwan Valley were declared a malaria-free zone in 1960 (CNP, 2018). This presented an opportunity for thousands of individuals to establish settlements in the Chitwan Valley. After the initial success of the malaria eradication efforts, extensive clearing occurred in the northern part of the valley, resulting in the loss of over two-thirds of the forest cover and grasslands (Gurung, 1983; Whalley, 1981). The human population density increased significantly, exerting immense pressure on natural resources, particularly forested habitats of tigers and one-horned rhinos (Gurung, 1983; Sharma, 1990). Within a relatively short period, these animals were on the brink of extinction in the Chitwan Valley (Gurung, 1983).

Fortunately, the region to the south of the Rapti River remained largely undisturbed (Whalley, 1981). The rapid decline of rhinoceros and other wildlife populations due to extreme poaching in the 1950s sparked international concern (CNP, 2018). Recognizing the potential threat, King Mahendra took action and declared the Mahendra Mriga Kunja (deer park) in 1959, covering 175 km² from the northern bank of the Rapti River

to the foothills of the Mahabharat range (present-day Barandabhar corridor forest) in Chitwan Valley (CNP, 2018). Likewise, in 1963, the area to the south of the Rapti River was officially announced as a Rhino Sanctuary (544 sq.km) (CNP, 2018). More than 22,000 local inhabitants were removed from the area and resettled outside the park boundaries (Mishra, 1982). Concurrently, the rhino patrol was launched with the aim of safeguarding the remaining rhinos, tigers, and other wildlife (CNP, 2018).

On the other hand, in the 1960s, the wild water buffalo and swamp deer became locally extinct from their native habitats in Chitwan Valley (CNP, 2018). The lush forests and grasslands of Chitwan Valley were cleared and converted into agricultural land, paving the way for new infrastructure developments. The population of the valley skyrocketed from 36,000 in 1950 to 185,000 by 1971 (CNP, 2018). The alarming rate of deforestation and loss of wildlife habitat prompted the government to enact the 1973 National Parks and Wildlife Conservation Act, a year after the Indian government enacted the Wildlife Protection Act, 1972, and a century after the establishment of Yellowstone National Park, which is regarded as the first national park in the world. Subsequently, the country established the Chitwan NP in 1973, as its first National Park to protect its last remaining rhino population and other wildlife (CNP, 2018; Nepal & Weber, 1995). In 1984, Chitwan NP was designated as a UNESCO World Heritage Site based on its outstanding universal value, as defined by criteria vii, ix, and x, UNESCO Ref:284.

The Chitwan NP has implemented many long-term and short-term projects since its establishment in 1973. In such The Nepal Tiger Ecology Project is one of the prominent one, which was commencing alongside with the establishment of the park in 1973 (CNP, 2018). The park was initially gazetted at 544 km². In 1977, the park was extended to 932 km² (CNP, 2018). In 1978, the Gharial Breeding Centre was initiated with the aim of reviving its declining population in the wild. Likewise, the Elephant Breeding Centre was established in 1985 to address similar concerns (CNP, 2018). Between 1980 and 1993, the Nepalese Government gifted 25 rhinos to six countries: India, Pakistan, Singapore, the United States, Germany, and Bangladesh (Jha et al., 1994).

The establishment of the park, along with stringent wildlife protection measures and restrictions on the use of natural resources that were previously accessible to the local inhabitants, exacerbated the conflict between the park and the people (Hemanta, 1982; Nepal & Weber, 1995; Sharma, 1990). These restrictions included limitations on collecting forest products, grazing livestock, and hunting and fishing. Incidents of crop loss, human and livestock losses due to wildlife from the park were the primary triggers of this conflict (Hemanta, 1982; Nepal & Weber, 1995; Sharma, 1990). The prioritization of wildlife over the local inhabitants by the park authorities affected the way of life of the local people (Sharma, 1990). Furthermore, the deployment of the

Nepalese Army in 1975 for park protection further exacerbated the conflict and resentment among the local inhabitants towards the park management (CNP, 2018; Hemanta, 1982; Nepal & Weber, 1995; Sharma, 1990).

In 1994, the Park People Programme was launched with the support of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). The program aimed to improve the socio-economic wellbeing of local communities around the park and conserve the park's biodiversity (CNP, 2018; HMGN & UNDP, 1994). Subsequently, in 1996, an area of 750 km², comprising forests, human settlements, and private lands surrounding the park, was designated as a Buffer Zone (CNP, 2018). The 1993 amendment of the National Parks and Wildlife Conservation Act, along with the Buffer Zone Management Regulations of 1996 and the Buffer Zone Management Guidelines of 1999, aimed to preserve the natural environment in buffer zones with the help and participation of the communities living in these areas (Stapp et al., 2015).

Communities living in the buffer zone of the park are permitted to enter the core area for a limited time at the beginning of each year to collect resources such as fodder grasses. They also practice controlled burning in some parts of the core area to regeneration of grasses (Murphy et al., 2013). Between 1998 and 2006, there had been extensive forest restoration in the buffer forests surrounding the park. The grazing of livestock in the buffer zone forest areas was ceased during this time, resulting in an increase in the amount of living matter in the forest and the abundance of prey within the buffer zone forests (Gurung et al., 2008).

In 2003, Beeshazar and the connected lakes situated in the northern buffer zone of the park were recognized as a globally significant Ramsar site, and in 2005, they were designated as Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBAs) by Bird Life International (CNP, 2018). Additionally, in 2014, the Chitwan NP was honoured with an international award from the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES). By 2014, the park had achieved the distinction of becoming the first global site to be granted Conservation Assured Tiger Standards (CA|TS) status. In 2016, the park was further extended to 952.63 km² (present-day size) by adding the Padampur area (CNP, 2018).

2.2 Location, topography, geology, and climate

The park and its buffer zone are located in the south-central region of Nepal (Figure 2.1), covering parts of four districts: Chitwan (74.04%), Parsa (15.45%), and Makawanpur (6.97%), and Nawalpur (3.54%). The park is situated between 27° 20' 19" and 27° 43' 16" north latitude and 83° 44' 50" and 84° 45' 03" east longitude. The buffer zone is located between 27° 28' 23" and 27° 40' 38" north latitude and 83° 43' 30" and 84° 45' 03" east longitude.

98" and 84° 77' 38" east longitude (CNP, 2018). The elevation of the park ranges from 150 to 815 meters above sea level. It is located in a river valley basin, with the Rapti, Reu, and Narayani rivers flowing through it.

Figure 2.1 Map of Chitwan National Park and its buffer zone showing the various land use and landcover details

The park is contiguous with Parsa National Park to the east, the Valmiki Tiger Reserve of India to the south, the lesser Himalaya in the north, and the Churia Mountain Range in the west. The forest corridor of Barandabhar and Daunne connects the park to the Churia range (CNP, 2018). The Churia hill ranges in Chitwan exhibit steep, rugged, and dissected terrain formed by sedimentary rocks, such as sandstone, mudstone, and conglomerates (Adhikari et al., 2019). This characterization of hill range divides the park into watersheds that drain into the Rapti, Reu, and Narayani rivers (Hemanta, 1982).

The Narayani, Rapti, and Reu Rivers are the main sources of water for the park. These rivers and other several small streams are essential for the park's wildlife. These rivers are also home to a variety of aquatic animals, including the critically endangered gharial and the Ganges river dolphin (*Platanista gangetica*) (CNP, 2018). The soil in the valley mainly consists of sandy and loamy textures, while in the south, one can find coarse bedded sandstone, crystalline rocks, clays, and conglomerates. Within the Park and its buffer zone, various types of soil can be observed, including brown shallow soil, brown, black and red soil, black soil, wet well-drained soil, poorly drained brown soil, and well-sorted dry shallow soil (CNP, 2018).

The park experiences four distinct climate seasons: summer, monsoon, autumn, and winter. Summer, which occurs from March to May, is characterized by very hot, dry, and westerly windy weather, with temperatures reaching as high as 37°C. The monsoon season lasts from June to September and brings heavy rainfall, with temperatures ranging from 25°C to 34°C. Autumn, from September to November, experiences slightly post-monsoon rain and moderate temperatures. Finally, winter spans from December to February and is the coldest season, with temperatures dropping as low as 8°C. December and January are the coldest months during this period (CNP, 2018). The Park receives an average annual rainfall of 2600 mm, with approximately 80% of the rainfall concentrated within the four-month period of the monsoon season (CNP, 2018).

2.3 Vegetation and wildlife

The park's vegetation is dominated by deciduous sal (*Shorea robusta*) forest, which covers 70% of the park. Other major vegetation types include grassland (10%), riverine forest (7%), mixed forest (7%), and wetlands (4%) (Paudel et al., 2022). Sal forests form pure stands in well-drained areas, notably in the lowlands around Kasara at the centre of the park. In other regions, Sal is found alongside longleaf Indian pine (*Pinus roxburghii*) on the southern slopes of the Churia Hills and is interspersed with various tree species, including chebulic myrobalan (*Terminalia chebula*), Indian rosewood (*Dalbergia latifolia*), axlewood (*Anogeissus latifolia*), Elephant apple (*Dillenia indica*),

and *Garuga (Garuga pinnata)* on the northern slopes (CNP, 2018). The under-storey is sparse, except for grasses like *Themeda (Themeda villosa)*. Riverine forests and grasslands, which create a mosaic along the riverbanks, are sustained by seasonal flooding.

The park boasts an impressive array of wildlife, including nearly 70 species of mammals, 49 species of reptiles and amphibians, over 541 species of birds, 120 species of fishes, and numerous invertebrate species (CNP, 2018). It serves as a prime habitat for Indian One-horned Rhinoceros, Royal Bengal Tiger and the Gharial. Additionally, it harbours the largest Asian terrestrial mammal, the Indian elephant, as well as the smallest mammal in Asia, the Pygmy shrew (*Sorex minutus*). Rhinos, spotted deer (*Axis axis*), and Indian hog deer (*Axis porcinus*) find their habitat in the floodplain grasslands and riverine forest, while the slopes adorned with Sal and mixed forests provide support to Sambar (*Cervus unicolor*), Gaur (*Bos gaurus*), and Barking deer (*Muntiacus muntjak*) (CNP, 2018). The flat regions covered with Sal and mixed forests are also inhabited by Spotted deer, Indian boar (*Sus scrofa cristatus*), and Barking deer. Carnivores are found throughout the park, but their distribution is influenced by the density of their prey and their position in the food chain. The Indian leopard however, are more likely to be found in the park's fringe habitats (CNP, 2018).

The Gharial can be spotted in the less disturbed areas of the Rapti and Narayani rivers, as well as along their banks. On the other hand, the Mugger crocodile (*Crocodylus palustris*), The Indian python (*Python molurus*), and yellow monitor lizard (*Varanus flavescens*) are commonly found in the wetlands of the park, including the swamps (CNP, 2018). Among the globally threatened bird species found in the park are the Bengal florican (*Houbaropsis bengalensis*), Slender-billed vulture (*Gyps tenuirostris*), White-rumped vulture (*Gyps bengalensis*), and Red-headed vulture (*Sarcogyps calvus*) (CNP, 2018). The park is home to 19 species of snakes, including some of the most venomous in the world, such as the king cobra (*Ophiophagus hannah*), the green pit viper (*Trimeresurus albolabris*), and the common krait (*Bungarus caeruleus*). The park also has a population of Indian python, which are the largest snakes in Asia (CNP, 2018).

2.4 Local communities and livelihoods

The park is under significant ecological pressure due to the surrounding villages in the buffer zone area (CNP, 2018). Historically, only a limited number of settlements were found within the present-day park, inhabited by indigenous Tharu, Bote, and Darai communities for centuries (CNP, 2018; Lamichhane et al., 2019b). However, the population of Chitwan district experienced a remarkable 274% increase from 1920 to 1980 (McDermott et al., 2023). This growth was primarily driven by migration from the hilly regions to the lowlands of Chitwan, resulting in a diverse demographic

composition in the buffer zone. This composition includes indigenous communities and migrants from the hill regions, encompassing high-caste Hindus (such as *Brahmins* and *Chhetris*), hill ethnic groups of Tibeto-Burmese origin (like *Tamangs*, *Gurungs*, and *Magars*), as well as marginalized lower-caste Hindus (including *Kamis*, *Damais*, *Sarkis*, etc.) (CNP, 2018; Lamichhane et al., 2019b).

At present, the buffer zone is home to 2,69,769 individuals and comprises 54,155 households (CNP, 2022). The majority of the local communities are dependent on agriculture and heavily rely on forest products for their livelihoods (CNP, 2018; Lamichhane et al., 2019b). Livestock husbandry is an integral part of subsistence agriculture among these communities, providing essential resources such as meat, dairy products, and manure support for farming activities. It serves as a significant source of livelihood and income in rural areas (Dhungana et al., 2019; Dhungana et al., 2018; Lamichhane et al., 2019b). The primary livestock include goats, sheep, cattle, pigs and buffalo (Dhungana et al., 2019). Additionally, some community members are engaged in wildlife tourism, service industries, and various businesses as alternative means of income generation. The buffer zone not only serves as an extended habitat for wildlife but also plays a crucial role in generating income for the local communities (CNP, 2018; Paudel et al., 2022).

3 Prioritizing human–wildlife conflict management strategies through importance-performance analysis: insights from Chitwan National Park, Nepal

Ferdin, A. E. J., Chandra Aryal, U., Dhungana, N., Ram Lamichhane, B., Chook, J. W., & Lee, C.-H.

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Abstract

Human–wildlife conflict affects the social-ecological systems essential for sustainable development. In human-dominated landscapes, effective management necessitates context-specific strategies that promote workable coexistence. This present study evaluates community perspectives on human–wildlife conflict management strategies through Importance-Performance Analysis in Chitwan National Park, Nepal. As a cost-effective and user-friendly tool, Importance-Performance Analysis helps protected area managers prioritize strategies and make informed decisions. Our findings reveal eight management strategies with significant importance-performance gaps, suggesting that park management is falling short in meeting both farmers’ and non-farmers’ needs. The graphical representation of Importance-Performance Analysis matrix visually identifies three high priority strategies—enhanced livelihood diversification skills, promotion of alternative livelihoods, and fast-tracked compensation schemes—that demand immediate action. The ANOVA results show varying perspectives between farmers and non-farmers across the park’s four management sectors (Kasara, Sauraha, Madi, and Amaltari), regarding the importance and performance of management strategies. This study demonstrates that Importance-Performance Analysis can be effectively adapted by protected area managers to evaluate and enhance management effectiveness from stakeholders’ perspectives, thereby balancing biodiversity conservation with community well-being and advancing the global goal of ‘living in harmony with nature’.

Keywords: Chitwan National Park, coexistence, human-modified landscapes, human–wildlife conflict, importance–performance analysis, Nepal, protected area management

3.1 Introduction

Human–Wildlife Conflict (HWC) has been identified as a significant challenge for biodiversity conservation and is also an obstacle to achieving sustainable development (Gross et al., 2021; IUCN, 2023). With the ongoing fragmentation and degradation of wildlife habitats, coupled with the amplifying effects of climate change, HWC is expected to increase in the future (Abrahms et al., 2023). However, the extent and severity of conflicts between people and wildlife differ greatly between developed and developing regions (Anand & Radhakrishna, 2017). In particular, the prevalence of HWC in developing countries is expected to escalate near Protected Areas (PAs) as both human and wildlife populations grow and the competition for resources intensifies with the human-modified landscape providing a new form of habitat for wildlife (König et al., 2021; Manfredo, 2015). The perspectives of the communities that share the landscape with wildlife play a crucial role in achieving workable coexistence (Ferdin et al., 2023; König et al., 2020). Because the negative interactions with wildlife on their property, agricultural fields, and where livestock are kept, can quickly undermine their support for and advantages from broader conservation objectives (IUCN, 2023).

Recognizing the complex dynamics of human–wildlife interactions, it is essential to consider not only the human-centric impacts of wildlife damage but also the broader context of coexistence where both wildlife and human communities can thrive. This approach emphasizes the integration of human attitudes towards wildlife into conservation strategies (Vogel et al., 2023). To improve residents' tolerance towards wildlife and to advocate for non-lethal control of HWC, the PA management should incorporate the aspects of socio-political and biophysical approaches (IUCN, 2023; Lamichhane, 2019; Nyhus, 2016). This has led to a collective consensus that involving communities who are key stakeholders in HWC as their livelihood is directly threatened by wildlife in decision-making is crucial to the long-term sustainable management of PAs (Ferdin et al., 2023; IUCN, 2023).

Nepal has been at the forefront of directly involving communities in forest management for over four decades (Paudyal et al., 2017). The buffer zones, which surround the national parks, was introduced in Nepal in 1996, through the amendment of National Parks and Wildlife Conservation Act 1973. These buffer zones encompass both forested and private lands, including agricultural areas and settlements (CNP, 2018; Ferdin et al., 2023). Their purpose is twofold: to provide an ecological and socio-economic buffer for wildlife in the park by offering additional (refuge) habitat, and local communities through community-based resource management (CNP, 2018; Lamichhane, 2019c). The buffer zones in Nepal's PAs serve as a benefit-sharing

mechanism, addressing various objectives such as mitigating HWC, promoting wildlife tourism, and ensuring conservation and sustainable development (CNP, 2018).

The prime objective of park management is to garner support from local community through a participatory approach. By motivating them to actively participate in conservation efforts, these buffer zones benefit both the community and wildlife (CNP, 2018). This approach underscores the sense of ownership that local communities have, positioning them as active partners in the co-management of PAs in Nepal. The Buffer Zone User Committees (BZUC) are key stakeholders in the park, acting as liaisons between the community and park management (Lamichhane, 2019c). They are responsible for providing support and compensation payments in cases of HWCs (CNP, 2018). The collective multi-stakeholder approach in Nepal has led to an increase in wildlife populations, including species such as the greater one-horned rhino (*Rhinoceros unicornis*), Royal Bengal tiger (*Panthera tigris*), and Asian elephant (*Elephas maximus*) among others (DNPWC, 2022). Unfortunately, this growth has also resulted in escalating negative interactions between communities and wildlife.

3.1.1 Application of Importance-Performance Analysis in wildlife management

The Importance-Performance Analysis (IPA) is a cost-effective, simple and strategic management tool, aids in prioritizing management strategies and fosters informed decision-making (Das et al., 2022; Martilla & James, 1977; Sever, 2015; Suárez-Rojas et al., 2023). It was initially developed to understand consumer satisfaction and to prioritize practical management actions (Sever, 2015). Over time, it has been applied in various fields such as transportation (Esmailpour et al., 2020; Rodriguez-Valencia et al., 2019), healthcare services (Izadi et al., 2017; Lu et al., 2020), and tourism management including park and ecotourism management (Bhalla & Bhattacharya, 2021; Taplin, 2012; Wade & Eagles, 2003). IPA is an affordable, well-documented, and widely accepted technique (Wade & Eagles, 2003), that has attracted the attention of environmental researchers worldwide (Das & Basu, 2020; Das et al., 2022; Hua & Chen, 2019). The IPA method plots people's views on the importance and performance of given strategies onto an easy-to-understand graphical presentation. It then categorizes these strategies into four quadrants, allowing for prioritization of HWC management strategies.

In the context of biodiversity conservation, the 'performance' aspect of IPA aligns with the effectiveness of PAs. Effectiveness, in this sense, refers to the degree to which PAs achieve their intended conservation outcomes. One critical factor associated with the underperformance of PAs is their level of management effectiveness. Strong evidence suggests that PAs are most successful in conserving biodiversity when they are well-

managed (UNEP-WCMC, 2017). Although IPA has not been traditionally applied in conservation, it can offer valuable insights to PA managers. For example, strategies deemed important for communities that share landscape with wildlife but are underperforming would undermine the effectiveness of PAs, as they are the cornerstone for biodiversity conservation (Karadeniz & Yenilmez Arpa, 2022). Conversely, strategies that perform well may indicate PAs that are managed effectively, thus positively impacting biodiversity conservation. Essentially, IPA provides a foundation for adapting performance measures to measure the success of conservation efforts within PAs under stakeholders' perception.

In recent years, IPA has been increasingly adopted in the field of environmental management due to its simplicity and ability to capture people's satisfaction regarding the importance and performance of management attributes. However, to the best of our knowledge, no empirical research has assessed the community's perceived importance and performance of various HWC management strategies in PAs within the South Asian region using IPA. We compared farmers and non-farmers due to their differing perspectives, interests, and experiences regarding HWCs. Farmers, whose livelihoods depend directly on subsistence agriculture, often suffer significant economic losses and agricultural damage due to negative wildlife interactions. On the other hand, non-farmers may have distinct concerns, such as fear of wildlife on their backyard or the impact of conflicts on their well-being. Understanding these contrasting viewpoints of different key stakeholders is crucial for developing comprehensive and inclusive strategies to effectively manage HWCs (IUCN, 2023; König et al., 2021).

Utilizing IPA approach Martilla and James (1977), this study aims to achieve three key objectives: (i) identify HWC management strategies that are important to communities, (ii) explore variations in the perception of importance and performance between farmers and non-farmers, and (iii) determine how these perceptions vary across different sectors of the park. Our innovative study provides a detailed blueprint for using IPA as a valid HWC management tool, not only in the South Asian region but also beyond. By allocating resources based on key stakeholders, park authorities can effectively address HWC and promote workable coexistence. These efforts have implications not only for South Asia but also for other regions facing similar conservation challenges.

3.2 Materials and Methods

3.2.1 Case Study: Chitwan National Park

This study was carried out in the buffer zone of Chitwan National Park (hereafter Chitwan NP), Nepal (Figure 3.1), is an UNESCO world heritage site. The park covers 953 km² and is surrounded by a 729 km² buffer zone (CNP, 2018). It was established as Nepal's first national park in 1973 (CNP, 2018). The park boasts a high diversity of rare and endangered wildlife, including the tiger, greater one-horned rhino, Asian elephant and Gharial crocodile (*Gavialis gangeticus*). Chitwan NP (and buffer zone) shares a ~100km border with India's Valmiki Tiger Reserve in the south (Figure 3.1), highlighting the importance of transboundary conservation efforts. The park management and its buffer zone are divided into four administrative sectors: Northern (Kasara), Eastern (Sauraha), Southern (Madi), and Western (Amaltari) for the effective management of the park. The management of the buffer zone is designed to address the site-specific socio-economic needs of local communities. It seeks to gain the support of those living within the buffer zone through participatory forest management. This strategy aims to reduce their reliance on forest resources, such as firewood, fodder for livestock, and grazing needs, thereby fulfilling their livelihood needs more sustainably.

Figure 3.1. Location map of Chitwan National Park, Nepal.

The 'conservation triangle model,' observed at the entrance of Chitwan NP, serves as a strategic framework for our understanding of sustainable conservation efforts within the park. This model, which is not widely discussed in the literature, illustrates the

collaborative roles of key stakeholders: the local community living in the buffer zone, park management, and the Nepalese Army. Each stakeholder is depicted as playing a crucial role in the effective management and conservation of the park's natural resources, aiming to achieve a balance between biodiversity conservation and meeting the socio-economic needs of the local communities.

The primary reason for selecting Chitwan NP as a case study is the increasing frequency of negative wildlife interactions experienced by communities in the park's buffer zone, which indicates a rise in HWCs (CNP, 2018). The park's conservation efforts have led to an increase in wildlife populations, while communities surrounding the buffer zone face threats and economic losses (CNP, 2018; Lamichhane et al., 2018). The majority of these communities depend on subsistence agriculture and forest products for their livelihoods. Consequently, crop damage has been the most frequently reported form of damage in Chitwan NP (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2 Total number of reported HWC incidents in Chitwan NP between fiscal years 2017 to 2023.

3.2.2 Methods: IPA for HWC management

To implement IPA in the context of Chitwan NP this study followed the four steps outlined by (Attarian, 1996): (i) identify a set of HWC strategies that are context-specific to the needs of Chitwan NP, (ii) conduct a survey in questionnaire form, requiring Chitwan NP communities to rate the importance and management performance for each HWC strategy on a five-point Likert-type scale, (iii) analyse data to determine the importance and performance values of each HWC strategy, and (iv)

plot a graphical representation of the performance and importance of individual HWC strategies as scored by the communities into four quadrant.

Traditionally, the IPA framework identifies four quadrants to assess the effectiveness of various strategies: 'keep up the good work' (Q1), 'concentrate here' (Q2), 'low priority' (Q3), and 'possible overkill' (Q4) (Martilla & James, 1977; Wade & Eagles, 2003). For this study, these quadrant names have been adapted to better align with the strategic focus of park management. The quadrants have been categorized as follows: 'Sustain' (Q1), 'High priority' (Q2), 'Low priority' (Q3), and 'Reallocate' (Q4) (Figure 3.3). Each label serves a specific purpose in the context of HWC management within Chitwan NP:

- Sustain (Q1): Aligning with 'keep up the good work', this quadrant identifies strategies that are effective and should be continued.
- High priority (Q2): Corresponding to 'concentrate here', this quadrant highlights strategies that are crucial but underperforming, requiring immediate improvement.
- Low priority (Q3): Consistent with 'low priority', this quadrant indicates strategies that are important but not urgent.
- Reallocate (Q4): Replacing 'possible overkill', this quadrant suggests strategies that may be ineffective or less impactful, where resources could be better utilized elsewhere.

By customizing these quadrant labels to our specific study context, we ensure that our recommendations align with the local context of Chitwan NP, making them actionable and relevant to protected area management.

Figure 3.3 The IPA grid for HWC management.

3.2.3 Strategy Design for HWC Management

The HWC strategies identified in this study are the result of a comprehensive review of literature on HWC management. Both the strategies and the corresponding literature sources are catalogued in Table 3.1. The selection of these strategies was guided by their relevance to the current challenges faced in HWC management in Chitwan NP, as well as their proven effectiveness in similar conservation contexts (König et al., 2020).

Among the identified strategies (Table 3.1), the implementation of ‘skill’ is underway in specific areas by Chitwan NP. However, the local municipality is also proactively involved in off-farm skills development—such as plumbing, carpentry, and electrician training—to diversify livelihood opportunities for residents. Collaboration with development agencies and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), including the National Trust for Nature Conservation (NTNC), World Wildlife Fund (WWF), and Zoological Society of London (ZSL), strengthens ‘resource’ allocation for community well-being. ‘Awareness’ workshops on HWC minimization, organized by Chitwan NP, the Community-Based Anti-Poaching Unit (CBAPU), NTNC, WWF, and other stakeholders, play a pivotal role. These workshops educate residents about biodiversity conservation and foster positive park-people ‘relationship’. Interestingly, park-people relationships thrive in areas with minimal HWC incidents, while communities from HWC-prone zones hold negative perceptions toward Chitwan NP.

Regarding ‘cultivation’, Chitwan NP management is experimenting with citronella (*Cymbopogon winterianus Jowitt*) plantation as a buffer crop. Citronella is unpalatable to wildlife and is currently being tested in the Madi Sector. ‘Compensation’ mechanisms are already in place, facilitated through the BZUC. However, the process remains time-consuming. Chitwan NP actively engages with communities to promote alternative ‘livelihood’ opportunities. These include nature guides, home-stay development, beekeeping, vegetable farming, and cattle rearing. By diversifying livelihoods, the park aims to foster sustainable coexistence between humans and wildlife. As for the ‘group’ aspect, which is a crucial part of any HWC management strategy, there are only two experts in the entire Chitwan NP who can dart problematic wildlife, covering the vast area. Chitwan NP, in coordination with NTNC-Biodiversity Conservation Centre, is responsible for handling problematic wildlife and acts as first-responders in the event of HWC. The park management is involving communities, park staff, and security personnel in the Rapid Response Teams (RRTs), ensuring a collaborative effort in managing HWC incidents.

Table 3.1 List of HWC management strategies.

No	Code	Strategies	References
1	Skill	Enhanced livelihood diversification skills	(Meyer & Börner, 2022; Sharma et al., 2021)
2	Resource	Ability to secure resources	(Gross et al., 2021; Hartter et al., 2011)
3	Awareness	Strengthen HWC awareness workshops	(Marker & Boast, 2015; Mekonen, 2020)
4	Cultivation	Cultivation of buffer crops	(Mekonen, 2020; Mukeka et al., 2019)
5	Compensation	Fast-tracked compensation schemes	(Karanth et al., 2018; Ravenelle & Nyhus, 2017)
6	Livelihood	Promotion of alternative livelihoods	(Bond & Mkutu, 2018; Gross et al., 2021)
7	Relationship	Improve park-people relationship	(Allendorf, 2020; Mutanga et al., 2017)
8	Group	Strengthening of rapid response teams	(Barlow & Brooks, 2019; Gross et al., 2021)

To ensure a robust and contextually appropriate design, we engaged with experts from the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), the Department of National Parks and Wildlife Conservation (DNPWC), Chitwan NP, NGOs, and independent consultants. These experts were consulted through semi-structured questionnaires, which were carefully developed to elicit insights on the current state of HWC, pinpoint significant management gaps, and gather recommendations for workable coexistence strategies. The semi-structured questionnaires were instrumental in validating the literature-derived strategies and adapting them to the specific socio-ecological dynamics of Chitwan NP. This iterative process of literature review and expert consultation ensured that the selected strategies are not only grounded in scientific

evidence but also tailored to the local context, thereby enhancing the potential for successful implementation, and achieving workable coexistence.

After the development of the structured questionnaires, we conducted a second round of consultations with the wildlife warden at Chitwan NP. This step was crucial for context-specific validation, ensuring that the questionnaires were precisely tailored to the unique socio-ecological conditions of Chitwan NP. The feedback from the park official was instrumental in refining the questions to better address the nuances of HWCs within the park's boundaries.

3.2.4 Research Instrument and Data Collection

We used a structured questionnaire to collect primary data. The survey questionnaire consisted of three sections. The first part accessed information related to HWC, the second part accessed the community's perception of HWC management strategies, and the third section included the socio-demographic information. The questionnaire (Appendix IV) was developed in English and conducted in Nepali. To ensure the validity of the questionnaire, we initially piloted the survey instrument with 50 residents living in the vicinity of the core zone of Chitwan NP (Perneger et al., 2015). We refined the survey questionnaire based on the feedback from the respondents and then validated it with the park and the NTNC- Biodiversity Conservation Centre staff.

All permissions to carry out the household survey in the buffer zone of Chitwan NP were obtained from the DNPWC, Nepal (Letter No: 131/078/79). All the procedures related to the household surveys strictly followed the guidelines as set by the DNPWC, Nepal and Chitwan NP Office (Letter No: 2003/078/79). Only the household members who had provided verbal consent and shown interest were interviewed.

In our study, we provided respondents with a clear explanation of the research topic and its objectives. To ensure a common understanding of HWC, we adopted the definition from the IUCN SSC Human–Wildlife Conflict Task Force. This definition describes HWC as the 'struggles that emerge when the presence or behaviour of wildlife poses actual or perceived, direct and recurring threat to human interests or needs, leading to disagreements between groups of people and negative impacts on people and/or wildlife' (IUCN SSC HWCTF, 2020). This definition was communicated to the residents in Nepali during the interviews to maintain consistency in the responses. Furthermore, the residents of the buffer zone are already familiar with the concept of HWC, having lived alongside wildlife and experienced its impacts firsthand. The park management has also been proactive in organizing awareness programs to sensitize the communities about minimizing HWCs. These efforts have contributed to a shared

understanding of HWC among the residents, which was reflected in their responses to our questionnaire.

This study adopted a stratified random sampling method to select a representative sample of households. The face-to-face quantitative survey covered households in 21 BZUCs, spanning four sectors across three districts (Chitwan, Nawalpur, and Parsa) (Figure 3.1). We obtained the population data from the park authority, which included 43,932 households across 21 BZUCs. This information was based on data available up to 2021. We were unable to obtain the household information for Gosaibaba BZUC. Consequently, we excluded this BZUC and conducted surveys in 21 other BZUCs. To ensure that each BZUC was adequately represented, we assigned a proportionate number of sampling units based on the percentage of households within each committee. This methodical approach allowed us to randomly interview a total of 506 households across 21 BZUCs, capturing a wide range of experiences and perspectives on HWC management strategies. By doing so, we aimed to reflect the diversity of the communities living in the buffer zone and to gather data that would be both comprehensive and applicable to the study's context and its objectives.

The formal survey was conducted during January-March 2022 by the second author, who is a buffer zone resident of the park. We maintained the survey hours as recommended by the park management, from sunrise to sunset on each day. The head of the household (male or female) was questioned. In the absence of an elderly member, an adult member of the family was questioned. Respondents were asked to rate their level of importance-performance on different strategies for HWC management.

The strategies used in the survey were already familiar to the respondents, as they had been localized to the specific context of Chitwan NP and reflected the situation at the time of the survey. The respondents easily understood the strategies presented by the second author, who also served as the enumerator. As a local resident of Chitwan NP (Sauraha), the second author's extensive knowledge of the area and its issues was an asset. Additionally, the enumerator's ability to communicate in both the indigenous Tharu language and Nepali was instrumental in establishing trust with the Tharu community, enabling the enumerator to gather genuine, unbiased information for the survey. Ultimately, we achieved a 100% response rate, underscoring the effectiveness of employing a local resident as an enumerator in developing countries like Nepal (Rai et al., 2019).

3.2.5 Statistical Analyses

The perceptions of the importance and performance of the HWC management strategies were quantified using a five-point Likert scale, with a range of 1 to 5 (i.e., strongly unimportant =1, unimportant =2, neutral =3, important =4, strongly important =5 for the importance rating; strongly disagree =1, disagree =2, neutral =3, agree =4, strongly agree =5 for the performance rating). At first, the arithmetic means of perceived importance and performance of the residents were calculated using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 26.0. We conducted paired t-tests between the means of importance and performance of the eight HWC management strategies. Second, the gap analysis was performed for statistical examination using mean performance minus the mean importance (P-I) (Taplin, 2012). Third, to achieve a consistent and meaningful comparison of the eight HWC management strategies, Z scores can be utilized (Das et al., 2022). By assigning a zero mean (origin), these scores allow for a statistically stable and effective standardization (Das et al., 2022). This standardization enables the assessment of the perceived importance, performance, and discrepancy of each strategies.

A higher Z score indicates a relatively higher level of perceived importance, performance, or discrepancy, while a lower score suggests the opposite (Das et al., 2022). Once we “standardized” the data we plotted the IPA matrix grid comparing farmers and non-farmers (perceived performance on x-axis and importance on y-axis) (Figure 3.3). In addition to the IPA, a two-way ANOVA was performed to determine the effect of the occupation and management sectors of the park management (independent variables) on the perceived importance and performance of the residents on the HWC management strategies (dependent variable).

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Socio-demography of the Respondents

Of the 506 respondents, 77% were farmers, and 33% were non-farmers. The sample included 169 indigenous (33%) and 337 non-indigenous (67%) residents. The majority of the respondents were male (57%). The largest number of respondents belong to the 40-49 years old age group (29%) followed by 50-59 years (29%), while the smallest was that of persons aged 60 or older. In terms of education, 54% are literate, and 46% are illiterate. As for the monthly income, most of the respondents were in the cohorts of 78.98 USD-118.46 USD (25%), while the lowest was 78.97 USD or less (Appendix IV).

3.3.2 HWC Incidents and Wildlife Involved

Out of 506 respondents, a significant majority (89%) reported experiencing HWC within the past five years. The types of conflict encountered were varied, with crop damage being the most common, affecting 447 respondents. This was followed by livestock depredation (64 instances) and property damage (27 instances). Notably, there were 5 instances of wildlife attacks on humans. These findings underscore the prevalent and diverse nature of HWC in Chitwan NP. It is important to note that in the survey, respondents were given the opportunity to select more than one type of damage they experienced due to HWC, which is reflected in the multiple incidents reported.

The wildlife species that were responsible for the HWCs in our study were spotted deer (*Axis axis*, 27%), greater one-horned rhino (26%), wild boar (*Sus scrofa*, 25%), elephant (9%), and Rhesus monkey (*Macaca mulatta*, 5%), as illustrated in Figure 3.4. Other species, comprising 8% include the nilgai (*Boselaphus tragocamelus*), Bengal fox (*Vulpes bengalensis*), Indian rock python (*Python molurus*), Indian peafowl (*Pavo cristatus*), Indian crested porcupine (*Hystrix indica*), and sloth bear (*Melursus ursinus*).

Figure 3.4 Proportion of wildlife species responsible for HWC incidents in Chitwan NP.

3.3.3 Importance-Performance Strategies: Farmers and Non-farmers

A paired t-test was carried out to examine whether any significant difference existed between the farmers and non-farmers on perceived importance and the performance scores of eight HWC management strategies (Table 3.2). All recorded importance scores were higher than the performance scores for both farmers and non-farmers

(Table 3.2). The two-tailed significance revealed that eight strategies were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the HWC strategies were very important to farmers and non-farmers. Still, the performance of park management did not meet their perceived expectations.

3.3.4 Importance-Performance Analysis Matrix Grid

We plotted a two-dimensional IPA matrix grid comprising four quadrants, comparing the perspectives of farmers and non-farmers (Figure 3.5). The IPA matrix reveals the following insights: Sustain (Q1): both farmers and non-farmers perceive resources and awareness strategies as necessary. Park management effectively implements these practices, reflecting their strengths in this quadrant. These strategies contribute positively to HWC mitigation and should continue. Notably, farmers consider the relationship strategy necessary, while non-farmers do not share the same perception. Park management should focus on improving this strategy to meet the needs of both groups. High priority (Q2): the strategies skill, livelihood, and compensation are considered high priority by both farmers and non-farmers. However, these strategies may currently fall short in performance. Allocating resources and efforts to enhance these areas is essential for effective HWC management. Low priority (Q3): group and cultivation strategies are perceived as low priority by both farmers and non-farmers. These strategies can be addressed over a longer timeframe, allowing park management to prioritize other pressing issues. Reallocate (Q4): non-farmers perceive that park management misuses resources in the relationship strategy (Figure 3.5). Reassessing and reallocating efforts in this area is necessary to improve HWC management. Park management should consider enhancing its performance in the relationship strategy to increase the satisfaction of non-farmers. Interestingly, farmers do not have strategies falling into this quadrant.

Table 3.2 Results of importance-performance analysis.

Code	Importance		Performance		Difference (P-I)	t-value	p-value
	Mean (I)	Std. Error	Mean (P)	Std. Error			
All residents (<i>n</i> = 506)							
Skill	4.747	0.022	1.678	0.050	-3.069	53.385	<0.001
Resource	4.759	0.022	2.099	0.062	-2.660	38.071	<0.001
Awareness	4.690	0.026	2.334	0.064	-2.356	32.826	<0.001
Cultivation	4.364	0.050	1.472	0.035	-2.892	42.894	<0.001
Compensation	4.721	0.026	1.389	0.031	-3.332	72.467	<0.001
Livelihood	4.747	0.023	1.395	0.034	-3.352	72.025	<0.001
Relationship	4.662	0.030	2.259	0.062	-2.403	33.115	<0.001
Group	4.536	0.043	1.504	0.036	-3.032	49.839	<0.001
Farmer (<i>n</i> = 392)							
Skill	4.714	0.027	1.651	0.055	-3.063	46.640	<0.001
Resource	4.735	0.026	2.094	0.070	-2.641	33.116	<0.001
Awareness	4.666	0.030	2.375	0.073	-2.291	27.961	<0.001
Cultivation	4.372	0.057	1.472	0.040	-2.900	38.563	<0.001
Compensation	4.704	0.030	1.372	0.033	-3.332	63.427	<0.001
Livelihood	4.722	0.027	1.362	0.035	-3.360	64.313	<0.001
Relationship	4.676	0.033	2.268	0.072	-2.408	29.568	<0.001
Group	4.543	0.047	1.520	0.041	-3.023	44.266	<0.001
Non-farmer (<i>n</i> = 114)							
Skill	4.860	0.035	1.772	0.114	-3.088	25.898	<0.001
Resource	4.842	0.036	2.114	0.136	-2.728	18.755	<0.001
Awareness	4.772	0.045	2.193	0.131	-2.579	17.499	<0.001
Cultivation	4.333	0.112	1.474	0.074	-2.859	18.937	<0.001
Compensation	4.781	0.051	1.447	0.080	-3.334	34.927	<0.001
Livelihood	4.833	0.041	1.509	0.091	-3.324	32.477	<0.001
Relationship	4.614	0.073	2.228	0.126	-2.386	14.930	<0.001
Group	4.509	0.101	1.447	0.076	-3.062	22.883	<0.001

Figure 3.5 Graphical representation of an IPA grid. The items coded in the grid are described in Table 3.1.

3.3.5 Perception on Management and Occupation

The ANOVA test indicated that occupation marginally affects the perceived importance of residents in HWC management strategies ($F(1,498) = 2.955, p = 0.086$) (Table 3.3). The non-farmers ($M = 4.693, SD = 0.437$) appeared to have slightly higher perceived importance than farmers ($M = 4.642, SD = 0.504$). Management sectors have statistically significant differences in the perceived importance of HWC management strategies ($F(3,498) = 14.225, p < 0.001$). The perceived importance of HWC strategies is higher in the Kasara sector ($M = 4.827, SD = 0.395$) compared to the Madi ($M = 4.708, SD = 0.424$), Eastern ($M = 4.695, SD = 0.503$) and Western sectors ($M = 4.401, SD = 0.516$) (Figure 3.6). However, the interaction effect of the occupation and management sectors ($O \times MS$) had no statistical significance for perceived importance of HWC management strategies of the residents.

Table 3.3 Two-way ANOVA tests on importance-performance by management sectors and occupation types.

Dependent variables	Independent variables	df	Mean Square	F-value (sig.)
Residents perceived importance of HWC management strategies				
Importance mean	Occupation (<i>O</i>)	1	0.633	2.955 (0.086)*
	Management Sectors (<i>MS</i>)	3	3.049	14.225 (0.000)***
	Interaction effect (<i>O</i> × <i>MS</i>)	3	0.217	1.011 (0.388)
Residents perceived performance of HWC management strategies				
Performance mean	Occupation (<i>O</i>)	1	0.054	0.108 (0.743)
	Management Sectors (<i>MS</i>)	3	4.605	9.288 (0.000)***
	Interaction effect (<i>O</i> × <i>MS</i>)	3	1.201	2.422 (0.065)*

Note: * $p < 0.1$, *** $p < 0.001$

Figure 3.6 Residents' perceived importance of HWC strategies across management sectors.

The occupation had no main effects on perceived performance of the residents in HWC management strategies (Table 3.3). The management sectors have statistically significant differences regarding the residents' perceived performance ($F(3,498) = 9.288, p < 0.001$) on HWC management strategies. The perceived performance of HWC strategies is higher in the Western sector ($M = 1.984, SD = 0.681$) compared to Eastern ($M = 1.806, SD = 0.752$), Kasara ($M = 1.633, SD = 0.683$) and Madi sectors ($M = 1.615, SD = 0.711$) (Figure 3.7). The interaction effect of the occupation and management

sectors ($O \times MS$) on perceived performance of the residents on different HWC management strategies was marginally significant ($F(3,498) = 2.422, p = 0.065$) (Table 3.3).

Figure 3.7 Residents' perceived performance of HWC strategies across management sectors.

3.4 Discussion

This study employed IPA to assess stakeholders' perspectives—both from farmers and non-farmers—regarding the importance and performance of eight HWC management strategies. By segmenting these two groups, we aimed to enhance the effectiveness of HWC management in Chitwan NP, Nepal. Additionally, we utilized ANOVA to understand their perceived importance and performance of park management across four different sectors. The main finding and the implication are as follows:

First, a gap analysis between the performance and importance of the HWC management strategies signifies the dire situation in relation to the park management handling of the HWC management (Table 3.2). This suggests that all the HWC management strategies did not meet the expectations, resulting in low satisfaction for farmers and non-farmers. The least satisfactory strategies for farmers and non-farmers

included skill, livelihood, and compensation related to their livelihood and social well-being (Table 3.2). The IPA analysis grid suggests that the strategies skill, livelihood, and compensation are considered high priority by both farmers and non-farmers (Figure 3.5) since they perceived these strategies to be more important for their livelihoods, indicating the need for the park management to focus on improving their performance in these areas. Fentaw and Duba (2017) recommend diversifying the livelihood opportunities of local communities that experience HWC, as it is a common approach to overcoming economic vulnerabilities caused by wildlife damages (Gautam & Andersen, 2016; IUCN, 2023). For instance, research in Bhutan has shown that communities reliant on a single income source, such as herders who depend solely on yaks and their products for livelihood, are less willing to coexist with wildlife when they lack the means to diversify their economic activities (Yeshey et al., 2023). This indicates that economic stability and the availability of multiple livelihood options can shape attitudes toward wildlife conservation and coexistence strategies (Habib et al., 2023). In response, Chitwan NP, in collaboration with key stakeholders, could provide targeted training and resources to both farmers and non-farmers. This would enhance their skills and address their livelihood needs, particularly when their economic stability, property, and well-being are at risk due to wildlife.

The effectiveness of compensation in HWC management is still debated (Dickman et al., 2011; Karanth et al., 2018; Ravenelle & Nyhus, 2017). However, countries around the world began to pay more attention to HWC compensation schemes, as it could jeopardize national conservation targets (Dickman et al., 2013). Although the Government of Nepal has been providing relief for wildlife victims throughout Nepal since 2009 (Lamichhane et al., 2018). Residents who were impacted by HWC feel that compensation is essential, but the process is lengthy, and the response is not sufficient compared to the losses incurred (Lamichhane et al., 2019b). For example, a study conducted in southern Kenya found that farmers affected by livestock predation expressed dissatisfaction with the government's response to their losses, citing it was inadequate to the actual losses they incurred (Anyango-Van Zwieten et al., 2015). Monitoring, standardizing, and implementing fast-tracked compensation schemes that reach all affected people in the community and reducing transaction costs can increase the tolerance of the local community towards wildlife and encourage coexistence (Karanth et al., 2018; Ravenelle & Nyhus, 2017). By focusing and facilitating community needs such as basic skill development, accelerated compensation fund and livelihood diversification, park management can make communities less vulnerable and enhance their ability to cope with HWCs (Frank & Glikman, 2019; König et al., 2020; Kushnir & Packer, 2019; Tsunoda & Enari, 2020). Second, the IPA grid revealed that the park management is performing well in the resource and awareness strategies (Figure 3.5). Both are perceived as important by farmers and non-farmers. This suggests that park

management has been helping local communities in securing resources to sustain their livelihood and well-being. This comes at a time when many HWC studies suggested that people and wildlife are increasingly competing for the same resources, especially in developing countries where resources are limited (Ferdin et al., 2023; Gross et al., 2021; Karanth et al., 2018; Kushnir & Packer, 2019; Megaze et al., 2017). Public awareness campaigns and workshops play a vital role in educating local communities about the values of wildlife and misperceptions about HWC (Gross et al., 2021; IUCN, 2023). The park management has successfully communicated the importance of wildlife conservation to the local community and should continue to maintain and strengthen the grassroots awareness programs. By emphasizing on the importance of resource security and educating community through grassroots level awareness programs, park management can increase awareness about the consequences of HWCs and empower communities to plan, learn, and adapt for workable coexistence with wildlife (König et al., 2020; Kushnir & Packer, 2019; Marchini et al., 2019; Tsunoda & Enari, 2020)

In the realm of PA management, establishing a harmonious relationship between the park and local communities is not only desirable but also essential (Allendorf, 2020). Our findings within Chitwan NP reveal a disparity in perceptions of this relationship between farmers and non-farmers, underscoring the complexity of conservation efforts in Nepal. The success of these efforts hinges on robust collaboration between the community and park management, particularly in addressing HWC (Pandey et al., 2016). Disagreements over interests, values, and needs between non-farmers and park management can potentially escalate into people-park conflict (IUCN, 2023).

Non-farmers, alongside farmers, play a pivotal role in Chitwan NP. However, restricting their traditional rights to access parks' core area for resources has led to adverse reactions, including incidents of rhino poaching (Adhikari et al., 2013). Despite being a minority, a significant number of non-farmers have encountered negative wildlife interactions. These non-farmers—daily wagers, fishermen, tour guides, forest guards, and office job holders—regularly encounter wildlife in their daily lives, whether during their commute, on their property, or at their workplace.

The active participation of non-farmers in BZUCs, alongside farmers, is crucial for fostering coexistence within the buffer zone. Strengthening the relationship between non-farmers and park management and offering them roles in CBAPU, RRTs and granting access to resources, can help align their interests with conservation goals. Given that poaching, along with HWCs, poses significant challenges in Chitwan NP (CNP, 2018), providing such opportunities is key to reducing the inclination for wildlife poaching and enhancing HWC management strategies (Adhikari et al., 2013). An inclusive approach that integrates insights from all community members, including

non-farmers, is crucial for crafting sustainable conservation outcomes that foster coexistence between humans and wildlife in Chitwan NP (Frank & Glikman, 2019; König et al., 2021). Interestingly, both farmers and non-farmers place lower priority on group and cultivation strategies, as shown in Figure 3.5. This suggests that the park management should re-evaluate their investment in these strategies and consider redirecting resources to other strategies in sustain and high priority quadrants. Such strategic adjustments are crucial for gaining support and active participation from both groups in conservation efforts.

Third, the two-way ANOVA conducted in this study indicated that the perceived importance and performance of the HWC management strategies varied among the parks management sectors (Table 3.3). This finding is consistent with similar studies conducted in communities bordering Africa's largest private wildlife reserve in Zimbabwe, where residents' perceptions varied according to their socio-demographic status (Makumbe et al., 2022). Due to its size, socio-economic and cultural setting, the park has been divided into four administrative sectors for effective management. Each sector is responsible for effectively and efficiently managing the park to deal with HWC and other management issues (CNP, 2018). The presence of wild animals can impose costs on local communities and undermine their support and tolerance for global conservation efforts (Barua et al., 2013). A study at Chebera Churchura National Park in Ethiopia found that socio-demographic factors likely influenced the attitudes of local residents (Megaze et al., 2017).

Given that the residents' perceptions on HWC strategies were likely influenced by socio-demographic factors, park managers could allocate revenue for compensation to more HWC-affected sectors, especially Kasara and Madi, where economic opportunities are limited. The communities in these sectors are more vulnerable to HWCs since their ability to cope with the risk is exceptionally high compared to the other two sectors. Park management should direct their attention on generating wildlife tourism revenues in these two highly vulnerable sectors and invest more resources in skill development to diversify their livelihood opportunities. We recommend the park management in prioritizing strategies that are customized to meet the diverse socio-demographic needs of the community and improve their overall performance levels in all sectors. Prioritizing HWC management strategies based on socio-demographic traits could help park management support local communities in coping with HWC and adapting their response to HWC (Frank & Glikman, 2019; König et al., 2020; Tsunoda & Enari, 2020). This could reduce their vulnerability and provide opportunities for planning, learning, and reorganization for future HWCs (König et al., 2020; Kushnir & Packer, 2019; Marchini et al., 2019; Tsunoda & Enari, 2020).

Finally, this study documented the widespread occurrence and high prevalence of HWC in Chitwan NP. It is evident that our respondents encountered HWC mainly in the form of crop damage, livestock depredation and property damage, as reported elsewhere in parts of Asia (Ashraf et al., 2022; Guru & Das, 2021; Thant et al., 2021), Africa (Long et al., 2020; Matseketsa et al., 2019; Mekonen, 2020), and South America (Zimmermann et al., 2021). The herbivores, such as elephants, rhinos, wild boar, and spotted deer, are the main conflict-causing species responsible for crop depredation in our study (Figure 3.4). Crop raiding by wild animals in Chitwan NP is a widespread and, major concern and it is on the rise (Figure 3.2).

It is crucial to recognize that the extent of damage and the subsequent compensation required can vary significantly depending on the species involved. A recent study by Lamichhane (2019c) observed that crop depredation by wild boars and spotted deer is frequent and widespread, imposing significant costs on the Government of Nepal and resulting in losses that are very hard to quantify. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the wild boar was only added to the relief guidelines in 2018. Nilgai and Rhesus monkey have been recently added to the revised relief guidelines by the DNPWC, effective from July 17, 2023. The impact of crop raiding by a herd of elephants may be vastly different from the damage caused by a group of Rhesus monkeys. Accordingly, the compensation mechanisms need to be adaptable to the scale and nature of the damage incurred in Chitwan NP. However, species such as spotted deer, Bengal fox, Indian peafowl, and Indian crested porcupine are not included in the revised list, highlighting a potential gap in addressing the full spectrum of HWC and its associated compensatory measures.

3.5 Conclusion

This study makes a significant contribution by assessing the perceptions of key stakeholders in Chitwan National Park regarding human–wildlife conflict management strategies, thereby informing decision-making. Through Importance-Performance Analysis, we aimed to identify crucial management strategies, explore differences in perceptions between farmers and non-farmers, and assess how these perceptions vary across the park's four management sectors. Our findings highlight the importance of strategies focusing on resources and awareness, as well as the need to enhance skills, livelihood, and compensation, which are high priorities for both stakeholder groups. This indicates key areas for improvement in HWC management within Chitwan National Park. Additionally, the differing perceptions among farmers and non-farmers across the park's four sectors underscore the need for sector-specific strategies for effective and targeted interventions.

Despite challenges and disagreements, there is potential for collaborative efforts between park management and local communities in Chitwan National Park. The human-modified landscape is not only home to local communities but also serves as an extended habitat for iconic wildlife. The survival of this wildlife depends on the park management, local communities, and the stringent conservation efforts provided by the Nepalese Army. Working together, they can strengthen the conservation triangle model, fostering a workable coexistence.

The insights gained from this research extend beyond Chitwan National Park, offering valuable lessons for protected area management worldwide. Protected areas are crucial for global biodiversity conservation, and this study emphasizes the value of Importance-Performance Analysis as a practical, cost-effective tool for evaluating the effectiveness of protected areas, particularly in the Global South where wildlife protection costs are high. By illustrating the application of Importance-Performance Analysis as a management tool, this study provides a replicable framework for protected area managers globally to identify and prioritize localized, context-specific strategies. Such an approach is likely to enhance conservation efforts and promote harmonious coexistence that mutually benefits both humans and wildlife in human-dominated landscapes.

Based on this study and our field observations, we provide specific recommendations to the park management that include: (1) develop tailored management plans that address the unique challenges within Chitwan National Park's distinct sectors, (2) engage with farmers to integrate their traditional knowledge and practices for species-specific and sector-specific human-wildlife conflict minimization, (3) streamline administrative procedures to simplify the relief process for claimants and expedite wildlife relief schemes promptly, (4) recognize the widespread and significant role of spotted deer in human-wildlife conflicts and include them in relief guidelines for a comprehensive approach, (5) promote non-invasive and wildlife-friendly physical barriers, such as beekeeping, buffer crops, and chili fencing, and evaluate their effectiveness across all sectors, (6) empower and support communities in establishing a community fund that can be utilized in case of delayed relief payments, thereby increasing victims' tolerance, (7) strengthen community involvement by increasing the number of volunteers in community-based anti-poaching units and rapid response teams, providing them with state-of-the-art training and incentives, (8) identify poor and marginalized farmers in each sector whose livelihoods are highly threatened by wildlife and train them in alternative livelihood opportunities to reduce their reliance on subsistence agriculture, (9) engage with non-farmers in each sector and involve them in conflict minimization activities, such as awareness campaigns and workshops, to improve the park-people relationship by fostering a sense of shared responsibility

among all community members, and (10) identify buffer crops that are also cash crops and studying their effectiveness across the park's four management sectors, learning from each sector's experiences with different wildlife species.

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Authorship contribution

Arockia E J Ferdin: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft (Lead), Visualization (Figures 3.2 – 3.7, All Tables), Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. Udit Chandra Aryal: Writing – review & editing, Data curation, Investigation, Project administration. Nabin Dhungana: Writing – review & editing, Visualization (Figure 3.1), Writing – original draft. Babu Ram Lamichhane: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. Jia Wei Chook: Writing – review & editing, Visualization (Figures 3.2 – 3.7, All Tables), Validation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. Chun-Hung Lee: Funding acquisition.

4 Understanding residents' preferences for adaptive capacity in human–wildlife coexistence: a case study from Nepal's biodiversity hotspot

Ferdin, A. E. J., Pathak, A., Kamaludin, M., Lamichhane, B. R., Shah, S. K., Aryal, U. C., & Baskaran, N.

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Abstract

Human–wildlife conflicts are exacerbated by the triple planetary crisis, as climate change, pollution, and biodiversity loss push wildlife into human-dominated landscapes, leading to increased competition for resources and heightened conflict. Thus, fostering human–wildlife coexistence in human-dominated landscapes, where wildlife has adapted to people, is of paramount importance. The people, who share space and resources with wildlife, face economic losses and threats to their well-being, through crop, and livestock depredations, human casualties, and psychological stress from safety concerns, yet exhibit remarkable behavioural plasticity. Understanding and implementing their preferences in coexistence will provide new insights that enhances mutual co-adaptation. With that in mind, this study aims to understand buffer zone residents' trade-offs using a discrete choice experiment in Chitwan National Park, Nepal. Our findings indicated a compelling preference among buffer zone residents to improve the current state of coexistence. The random parameters logit model revealed that grassroots-level awareness programmes, promoting sustainable economic opportunities, integrating science with indigenous knowledge, and rapid response teams were the most preferred strategies to enhancing the adaptive capacity of communities to coexist with wildlife. We anticipate that our findings will aid the Chitwan National Park management in fostering successful co-adaptation strategies that benefit both buffer zone residents and the wildlife sharing these human-dominated landscapes.

Keywords: Adaptive capacity, Agricultural landscapes, Chitwan National Park, Coexistence preferences, Human–wildlife conflict, Protected area management

4.1 Introduction

Human–wildlife conflicts (HWCs) are increasing globally, especially in agricultural areas where people and wildlife that have adapted to human-dominated landscapes, compete for space and resources (Dickman, 2010; Redpath et al., 2015). Growing emphasis on tolerance and coexistence has shown that wildlife can thrive in human-dominated landscapes, and many human–wildlife interactions, though competitive, do not always result in conflict (Frank & Glikman, 2019). Human–wildlife coexistence is a dynamic state in which humans and wildlife co-adapt to a shared landscape, with conflicts being understood, tolerated, and well-managed in legitimate ways to ensure the long-term recovery of wildlife populations and generate co-benefits (N. H. Carter & J. D. Linnell, 2016; IUCN, 2023). Nevertheless, facilitating coexistence is not only about reducing conflicts, but also about enhancing the mutual benefits that both humans and wildlife can derive from shared landscapes. This is essential, as the human–wildlife interface is expanding due to factors like habitat fragmentation and degradation, encroachment, linear infrastructure, and climate change (Acharya et al., 2017; Frank & Glikman, 2019; Hill, 2021; Nyhus, 2016; Pooley et al., 2021). Therefore, there is a demanding need to promote human–wildlife coexistence, that generates co-benefits, especially in human-dominated agricultural landscapes which border protected areas (Carter & Linnell, 2023; Killion et al., 2021; Pooley et al., 2021).

Wildlife have shown remarkable behavioural plasticity, allowing them to adapt to human-dominated agricultural landscapes (Johann et al., 2020; Srivastava et al., 2020). For instance, the Indian leopard (*Panthera pardus*) is a versatile carnivore capable of altering its diet to survive in human-dominated landscapes, often consuming domesticated animals such as feral dogs rather than wild prey (Athreya et al., 2016; Kumbhojkar et al., 2021). This dietary shift facilitates human–leopard coexistence by providing beneficial ecological and public health services, including controlling feral dog populations. Reducing feral dog numbers can lower the incidence of rabies, a significant public health concern in India, and decrease predation pressures on local wildlife (Braczkowski et al., 2018). Conversely, humans also demonstrate strong adaptability for coexisting with wildlife (N. H. Carter & J. D. C. Linnell, 2016; Carter & Linnell, 2023). For example, humans employ non-lethal management strategies (Killion et al., 2021), perceive wildlife as an economic resource to generate additional income (Gordon, 2009), and adapt wildlife-friendly agricultural practices (Tshewang et al., 2021). This highlights that adaptations from both wildlife and humans can foster co-benefits, creating mutually beneficial outcomes in shared landscapes. Carter and Linnell (2023) emphasise enhancing the capacity for wildlife to adapt to human-modified landscapes, while also advocating for humans to retain, relearn, and innovate new strategies to strengthen their adaptive capacity toward wildlife. In essence,

adaptive capacity is a valuable concept for resource managers, users, scientists, and policymakers alike to address the growing conservation challenges (Plummer & Armitage, 2010).

Although human–wildlife coexistence can generate co-benefits, cases where adaptation has failed highlight key challenges. For instance, pastoralists in Laikipia District, Kenya, who experienced severe crop damage and feared living alongside elephants, resisted conservation efforts and supported elephant culling when elephants killed humans or raided crops, exacerbating conflict (Gadd, 2005). Similarly, farming households in Botswana showed little interest in safeguarding wildlife through anti-poaching activities due to low economic incentives (Mogomotsi et al., 2020). These examples emphasise that limited economic benefits have hindered local community tolerance and adaptation to wildlife, making coexistence more difficult. Recognising and addressing the barriers that prevent communities from sustaining their livelihoods and well-being is essential for encouraging wildlife tolerance and stewardship, ultimately leading to successful human–wildlife coexistence.

In an ecological context, adaptive capacity refers to a system’s ability to withstand unexpected changes and substantial transformations (Armitage, 2005). In a social context, however, adaptive capacity refers to the ability of individuals or communities, organisations, and institutions to learn and adapt to change (Berkes, 2007; Folke et al., 2003). Fostering adaptive capacity can significantly enhance the overall adaptive level of societies, as they are more likely to have the knowledge, skills, and understanding required to respond effectively to environmental changes (Fazey et al., 2007; Tengö & Heland, 2011). Communities with low adaptive capacity may be less able to adapt to changes in resource availability, for example less likely to comply with conservation measures that restrict resource use (McClanahan et al., 2008). For instance, in the Philippines and South Africa, a disparity between wildlife conservation and the community’s adaptive capacity, resulted in increased conflict and reduced cooperation between local communities and protected area governing bodies (Cavalier et al., 2022). This imbalance was evident in societies living near crocodylian habitats, where conservation policies prioritised species protection but often overlooked the socio-economic realities of affected communities (Daltry et al., 2016). These challenges illustrate the critical need to balance conservation goals with the adaptive capacity of local community members to foster coexistence.

Nepal, a mountainous and landlocked country in the central Himalayas, faces significant challenges in promoting human–wildlife coexistence. The country’s protected areas were primarily established to conserve large mammals (Baral et al., 2021), and Nepal has made remarkable strides in reviving threatened species. For example, the greater one-horned rhinoceros (*Rhinoceros unicornis*) population has

surged from around 100 individuals in the early 1960s to 752 in 2021, while the Royal Bengal tiger (*Panthera tigris*) population has increased from 121 in 2009 to 355 in 2022. Additionally, the Asian elephant (*Elephas maximus*) population augmented substantially, from approximately 50 individuals in the 1990s to 227 in 2020 (DNPWC, 2022). However, this growth in wildlife populations, alongside factors such as human population expansion, encroachment, and linear infrastructure, has significantly altered the landscape. Additionally, the conversion of land into agricultural fields has created new, and destroyed former habitats and increased the interface between humans and wildlife, which has ultimately led to frequent HWCs across the country (Acharya et al., 2017; Acharya et al., 2016; Bhattarai et al., 2019). For instance, between 2000 and 2020, Nepal recorded approximately 1,139 fatalities among large mammals and 887 human casualties resulting from these conflicts (Baral et al., 2021). These statistics highlight the urgent need for innovative strategies to promote coexistence in Nepal's biodiversity hotspots (Ferdin, 2024a).

There is a growing interest in incorporating human dimensions to facilitate coexistence with wildlife, with non-market valuation methods frequently applied to understand people's preferences (e.g., Mzek et al., 2022; Notaro & Grilli, 2022; Subroy et al., 2018). Among these, discrete choice experiments, a commonly used non-market valuation method, are often used to inform decision-making, as demonstrated in recent studies on community preferences for coexisting with species like jaguars in Mexico (Gordillo-Chávez et al., 2025), elephants in Tanzania (Montero-Botey et al., 2021), and wolves in the USA (van Eeden et al., 2021). Discrete choice experiments ask respondents to choose their most preferred option from a series of hypothetical scenarios or alternatives, each defined by different attributes and levels, with the aim of informing policy decisions (Hanley et al., 2001; Holmes et al., 2017).

This study utilises a discrete choice experiment to address the following primary research question: *what are respondents' overall preferences for strategies that enhance their adaptive capacity to coexist with wildlife?* The secondary research question is: *which demographic groups are more likely to prefer those strategies?* By analysing how residents evaluate trade-offs between different management strategies, the study seeks to unearth insights that can inform policy decisions, ensuring they better align with local preferences. The discrete choice experiment design incorporates adaptive capacity indicators as choice attributes, with socio-demographic characteristics included to enable analysis of preference variations across demographic groups, particularly indigenous communities given their cultural and conservation significance in Chitwan National Park. This approach distinguishes the study from existing discrete choice experiments through its novel use of adaptive capacity theory to structure choice attributes, offering evidence-based insights to

support global efforts in minimising HWCs and promoting coexistence, for example within the Global Biodiversity Framework's Target 4 (<https://www.cbd.int/gbf/targets/4>).

4.2 Materials and methods

4.2.1 Case study: Chitwan National Park

Chitwan National Park (Chitwan NP), established in 1973, is the oldest National Park of Nepal and a UNESCO World Heritage Site (Figure 4.1). Chitwan NP hosts the second-largest population of the greater one-horned rhinoceros globally, after Kaziranga National Park in India. Located in the south-central part of the country, (27°16.56' – 27°42.14'N and 83°50.23' – 84°46.25'E), Chitwan NP covers an area of 953 km² (CNP, 2018). The park is the first site globally to be accredited with the CA|TS (Conservation Assured Tiger Standard) award for its significant role in the conservation of tigers and their habitat. The park shares a contiguous boundary with Parsa National Park to the east and India's Valmiki Tiger Reserve to the south. It is a part of the Terai Arc Landscape, a transborder conservation initiative that geographically spans the lowlands of Nepal and India.

Figure 4.1 Map of the location of Chitwan National Park, south-central Nepal. Our study site is divided into four administrative sectors: Northern (Kasara), Eastern (Sauraha), Southern (Madi), and Western (Amaltari).

The park has a monsoon dominated sub-tropical climate with an average monthly maximum temperature between 24°C – 38°C, monthly minimum temperature

between 11°C – 26°C and annual rainfall ~ 2250 mm. The majority of the park (>70%) is covered with Sal (*Sorea robusta*) dominated forests. Three Rivers - Narayani, Rapti, and Reu Rivers and their tributaries drain the park and are crucial for providing water to the park's wildlife. Highly productive alluvial grasslands and riverine forests along these rivers support a high density of various wildlife. The park is well known for its biodiversity, with a species diversity of over 70 mammals, 600 birds, 56 reptiles and amphibians, 156 butterflies, and 120 fishes. Chitwan NP is home to a range of globally threatened terrestrial wildlife, including elephants, rhinoceros, tigers, sloth bears (*Melursus ursinus*), and pangolins (*Manis crassicaudata* and *M. pentadactyla*). Its rivers are also home to a variety of threatened aquatic wildlife, including the Gharial crocodile (*Gavialis gangeticus*), mugger crocodile (*Crocodylus palustris*) and the Ganges River dolphin (*Platanista gangetica*).

The buffer zone (BZ) of the Chitwan NP was established in 1996 through an amendment to the National Parks and Wildlife Conservation Act of 1973. The purpose of the BZ was to make forest resources accessible to local communities and provide additional habitat for wildlife. Furthermore, the amendment provisioned 30 – 50% of the park revenue for the BZ programme to support community development and conservation initiatives. The BZ covers an area of 750 km² around the park (~ 21 km² was later merged into the park in 2017). It is home to 269,769 individuals comprising 54,155 households (CNP, 2022). Mixed communities of hill immigrants and indigenous ethnic groups such as the Tharu, Bote, Darai, and Majhi live in the BZ (CNP, 2018). Chitwan NP and its BZ are divided into four administrative sectors: Northern (Kasara), Eastern (Sauraha), Southern (Madi), and Western (Amaltari) (Figure 4.1). A total of 22 BZ user committees were formed in Chitwan NP in 1996. The BZ user committees are important stakeholders in Chitwan NP, as depicted in the conservation triangle model (for more details, see Ferdin et al., 2024b). This collective multi-stakeholder approach involving BZ residents, the Nepalese Army, and the park has led to an increase in wildlife populations in Chitwan NP. The long-term goal of the BZ user committees is to address the socio-economic needs of local community members and engage them in wildlife conservation efforts (CNP, 2018).

However, challenges persist. The local community's heavy dependence on subsistence agriculture and forest resources has resulted in substantial impacts on the BZ residents, including increased crop damage, livestock depredation, human casualties, and property damage (CNP, 2018; Ferdin et al., 2024b). These conflicts have also taken a severe toll on wildlife, with 341 wildlife mortalities reported between the fiscal years 2017 and 2023, including species such as rhinoceros, bears, tigers, and leopards,

among others.¹ Furthermore, illegal forest resource extraction, driven by increased demand from rapid population growth and compounded by natural causes, has led to habitat degradation and loss, threatening the ecological integrity of Chitwan NP (Bhattarai & Kindlmann, 2013; Carter et al., 2013; Nagendra et al., 2008). Despite these challenges, the park management strives to foster coexistence where local communities and wildlife can thrive in a shared landscape (Ferdin, 2024a).

4.2.2 Discrete choice experiment

4.2.2.1 Selection of attributes and their levels

We designed a discrete choice experiment that includes four attributes, derived from the four indicators of adaptive capacity proposed by Folke et al. (2003): (1) learning to live with change and uncertainty, emphasises dealing with the uncertainty associated with conflicts and taking advantage of past events to manage conflicts (for example Jochum et al., 2014; Wiczorek Hudenko, 2012); (2) nurturing diversity in its various forms, underscores the importance of diverse collaborations in enhancing livelihoods of people (for example Berkes, 2007; Distefano, 2005); (3) combining different types of knowledge and learning, highlights the significance of integrating different knowledge systems necessary for local inhabitants to coexist with wildlife (for example Hussain et al., 2022; Lewis et al., 2016); (4) creating opportunity for self-organisation and cross-scale linkages, underscores the need for the local community's self-organisation to cope with conflicts (for example Berkes, 2007; Uddin et al., 2021); and willingness to participate as the fifth attribute (Table 4.1).

¹ Data regarding human-wildlife conflict incidents were compiled from Chitwan National Park annual reports for the fiscal years 2017 to 2023.

Table 4.1 Attributes and levels included in the discrete choice experiment for eliciting residents' preferences in human–wildlife coexistence.

Attributes	Levels	Variables
Learning to live with change and uncertainty	Inadequate skills to mitigate human–wildlife conflict*	
	Organise grassroots-level awareness programmes	Awareness
	Incorporate land-use planning in coping strategies	Planning
Nurturing diversity for reorganisation and renewal	Limited economic opportunities at the grassroots-level*	
	Diversify partners and cooperation to enhance economic opportunities	Diversify
	Promote sustainable economic opportunities to improve livelihoods	Sustainable
Combining different types of knowledge for learning	Inadequate skills to coexist with wildlife*	
	Integrate science with indigenous knowledge and practices	Knowledge
	Combine information and communication technologies with local information sharing system	Technology
Creating opportunities for self-organisation	Limited ability to reorganise in the event of human–wildlife conflict*	
	Strengthening of rapid response teams	Team
	Establishing a community fund	Fund
Willingness to participate	Zero hours*, 3, 5, 7 and 10	Hour

Note: 1. *Status quo. 2. The first four adaptive capacity indicators used as attributes were adapted from Folke et al. (2003)

The levels, three for each of the four attributes, were identified based on in-depth face-to-face interviews conducted with key stakeholders. These included the Chief Wildlife Warden of Chitwan NP, a Conservation Officer at the Department of National Parks and Wildlife Conservation (DNPWC) (the administrative authority for protected area management), and representatives from the National Trust for Nature Conservation (NTNC) (an autonomous institution that assists the DNPWC in Nepal). These consultations ensured that the attribute levels reflected realistic and context-specific management options for human–wildlife coexistence in the region.

Although willingness to participate in implementing the proposed coexistence strategies was included in the design of the discrete choice experiment as the fifth attribute, its primary purpose was to assess respondents' threshold for engagement rather than as a central outcome of interest. The main analytical focus of our study is understanding the trade-offs respondents make across various coexistence strategies, similar to (Montero-Botey et al., 2021), who explored rangers' trade-offs for different conflict mitigation strategies without a monetary attribute.

An orthogonal main effects design was used to generate the choice cards for this study (Louviere, 2000). Ensuring orthogonality in choice experiment design is important as it allows for the independent estimation of the effect of each attribute on respondents' choices, thereby minimising confounding effects and enhancing the reliability of the results. We utilised IBM SPSS 26.0 to determine the number of alternatives in our discrete choice experiment design.

4.2.2.2 Questionnaire design

The questionnaire consisted of three sections (see Appendix V). The first section included warm-up questions designed to stimulate respondents' interest, establish rapport, and create a comfortable atmosphere before engaging in the choice tasks. The second section presented the discrete choice experiment. The orthogonal main effects design reduced the number of choice tasks from a full factorial of 25 to 12 statistically efficient choice tasks, ensuring balanced representation of all attribute levels while maintaining orthogonality. These 12 unique choice tasks were then organised into 22 versions, which were randomly distributed to respondents. Each respondent was presented with three choice tasks from their assigned version, each accompanied by illustrations to minimise cognitive burden. For each choice task, they were required to select from three alternatives: two proposed coexistence strategies and one status quo option (see Figure 4.2 for an example). The final section collected respondents' socio-demographic characteristics.

CHOICE SET 2			
	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Status quo
Learning to live with change and uncertainty	Inadequate skills to mitigate HWC 		
Nurturing diversity for reorganisation and renewal	Limited economic opportunities at the grassroots-level 		
Combining different types of knowledge for learning	Combine ICTs with local information sharing system 		
Creating opportunity for self-organisation	Strengthening of rapid response teams 		
Willingness to Participate	5 hours / week	10 hours / week	0 hours / week
Please Tick	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 4.2 Example choice card used in our study.

4.2.2.3 Data collection

Pilot study A pilot study was conducted in March 2022 with 50 randomly selected BZ residents of Chitwan NP to assess their understanding of the choice cards, given that many had likely never encountered one before. Respondents had little to no difficulties understanding the questions or completing the choice cards. However, respondents' understanding varied across different community groups. Those directly affected by wildlife incidents and educated individuals, typically those with schooling beyond the high secondary level, grasped the scenarios easily. Indigenous communities, such as the Tharu and Bote, faced more challenges, as they viewed conservation policies as restricting their ancestral rights and access to park resources. Older respondents also required more explanation and were generally less optimistic about providing responses.

Sampling design and main survey implementation Building on these insights, the main survey was conducted between March and May 2022 as a face-to-face quantitative study in Nepali. Each interview lasted approximately 30 minutes on average. Using population data from the park authority (43,932 households as of 2021), we systematically sampled 506 households across 21 BZ user committees, excluding the Gosaibaba BZ user committee, where household information was unavailable at the time. This exclusion, due to logistical challenges and unavailability of updated records, is unlikely to significantly impact the study's representativeness.

We employed stratified random sampling to ensure inclusivity and robust representation of households across diverse communities in the study area. Sampling units were proportionally allocated based on the percentage of households in each BZ user committee. The minimum required sample size of 384 was determined with a 95% confidence level and a 5% precision, assuming an estimated proportion (p) of 0.5 and a margin of error (e) of 0.05. Our final sample size of 506 exceeded this requirement, enhancing the statistical power while reducing the margin of error, thereby increasing both reliability and precision. Additionally, the larger sample size helps account for potential non-responses or incomplete data.

Participant selection For participant selection, enumerators approached the head of the household (male or female) for the interview. If an elder member was unavailable, a family member over the age of 18 was interviewed instead. All enumerators were native to Chitwan NP, bringing extensive knowledge of the study area and its HWC issues. This local expertise was instrumental in establishing trust with respondents, enabling the enumerators to gather genuine, unbiased information for the survey. By using enumerators who were native residents of the area, we achieved a 100% response rate. The incorporation of localised knowledge and language into the survey design, we maximised engagement and minimised barriers to participation.

4.2.2.4 Ethical approvals and permissions

All necessary permissions for conducting the household survey were obtained from the DNPWC (Letter No: 131/078/79, dated 12-JAN-2021) and the Chitwan NP office headquarters in Kasara (Letter No: 2003/078/79, dated 14-JAN-2021). We strictly adhered to the guidelines set by the DNPWC and Chitwan NP Office. Respondents were provided with information about the research topic and its objectives, and only those who gave verbal informed consent were interviewed.

4.2.2.5 Model specification and choice response analysis

The analysis of residents' preferences for human–wildlife coexistence in this study is based on the random utility theory, a foundational concept in discrete choice experiments. The theory was introduced by Thurstone (1927) and further developed by McFadden (1972), and offers a robust framework for understanding how individuals make choices among alternatives. According to the random utility theory, individuals are assumed to select the option or alternative that maximises their utility. The utility that an individual i derives from selecting an alternative j in a choice set is composed of two components; a deterministic part (V_{ij}) that can be observed, and a random error term (ϵ_{ij}) which captures unobserved factors. The utility can be demonstrated as follows:

$$U_{ij} = V_{ij} + \epsilon_{ij} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where U_{ij} is the total utility derived from alternative j , V_{ij} is the observable component, often modelled as a function of the attributes of the alternatives and characteristics of the individual, and ϵ_{ij} is the unobservable (random) component, assumed to be independently and identically distributed (i.i.d.). McFadden (1972) Conditional Logit (CL) model, relying on the Type I Extreme Value (Gumbel) distribution, leads to the multinomial logit model. Nevertheless, the CL model's restrictive Independence of Irrelevant Alternatives (IIA) property hinders its flexibility in capturing realistic substitution patterns between alternatives.

Researchers frequently apply the Random Parameters Logit (RPL) model, sometimes referred to as the mixed logit model, to address the limitation. This model extends the standard logit framework by allowing for random taste variation among individuals. This indicates that the coefficients on the attributes of the alternatives are not fixed but are treated as random variables that differ from individual to individual. The RPL model is appropriate for modelling more complicated preference structures since the random parameters permit variable substitution patterns and avoid imposing the limited IIA assumption. According to the RPL model, the utility function is as follows;

$$U_{ij} = \beta_i X_{ij} + \epsilon_{ij} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where X_{ij} is the vector of attributes for alternative j , β_i is the vector of random coefficients that vary across individuals i , capturing preference heterogeneity among respondents, and ϵ_{ij} is the i.i.d. error term.

An alternative-specific constant (ASC_{SQ}) was included in all models to represent respondents' inherent preference or bias toward the status quo scenario relative to the proposed alternatives. The ASC_{SQ} captures the baseline preference for maintaining the current situation, independent of specific attribute trade-offs, thus revealing how

respondents' preferences shift when presented with alternatives different from the status quo (Holmes et al., 2017; Morrison et al., 2002). A negative ASC_{SQ} indicates that respondents prefer the proposed alternatives over maintaining the current situation.

The RPL model is an extension of the random utility theory, offering a richer and more flexible framework to analyse choice behaviour by accounting for individual-level heterogeneity (Greene & Hensher, 2003). This flexibility makes it particularly useful in human–wildlife coexistence studies, where understanding respondent's trade-offs is crucial. This model has the advantage of not being constrained by the IIA assumption, thus offering increased flexibility that allows us to capture unobserved heterogeneity in preferences across respondents (Birol et al., 2006; Kaffashi et al., 2012). Several studies have applied RPL in this context, including Gordillo-Chávez et al. (2025) and Montero-Botey et al. (2021).

The choice response data were analysed using NLOGIT/LIMDEP 5.0. From the estimation output, the CL model served as a baseline for comparison. Subsequently, both the RPL model and the RPL model with interactions were estimated. In the RPL model, all attributes, except willingness to participate, were specified as random parameters with normal distributions to capture preference heterogeneity among respondents. To gain deeper insights into the sources of preference heterogeneity, we developed an RPL with interactions model, where key socio-demographic characteristics, including age, gender, indigenous status, education level, and monthly income, were interacted with the ASC_{SQ} .

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Backgrounds of sampled respondents

The respondents were predominantly male, making up 60% of the sample (Table 4.2). Around 63% of respondents identified as non-indigenous. On average, respondents were 41 years old ($SD = 9.86$) and reported a monthly income of NPR 20,469 ($SD = 7,652$), approximately USD 151. Their households typically consisted of about five members ($SD = 1.76$), reflecting the average family size. Notably, over half of the respondents (57%) had attained an education level of middle school or higher (Table 4.2).

Table 4.2 Respondents' socio-demographic characteristics (N = 506).

Variables	Description	Mean (SD)	Number (%)
Gender	Male coded as 1, female coded as 0	-	305 (60%)
Indigenous status	Indigenous coded 1, non-indigenous coded 0	-	188 (37%)
Education level	Middle school and above coded 1, primary school and below coded 0	-	287 (57%)
Age	Average age of the respondents in years	41.047 (9.860)	-
Monthly income	Average monthly income of the respondents in NPR	20469.368 (7652.059)	-
Family size	Average number of family members per household	5.213 (1.761)	-

Note: 1. Standard deviation (SD) and percentage (%) values are provided in parentheses.

2. NPR is Nepalese Rupees; USD 1 = NPR 134.81 on October 19, 2024, as per the Nepal Rastra Bank (<https://www.nrb.org.np/>).

4.3.2 Econometric results

Table 4.3 presents results from the CL, RPL, and RPL interaction models. Compared to the baseline CL model (log likelihood = -1481.312; Pseudo R^2 = 0.045), both RPL models significantly improve the explanatory power. Comparing the two RPL models, the interaction model demonstrates modest but notable improvements: the log likelihood improves from -1165.680 to -1158.850, and the Pseudo R^2 slightly increases from 0.301 to 0.305 (Table 4.3).

There was significant preference heterogeneity in both RPL models (as shown by the significance of the standard deviation estimates) (Table 4.3). In both RPL models, the ASC_{SQ} is significantly negative. Each of the four adaptive capacity attributes had at least one statistically significant level. Overall, the respondents prefer organising grassroots-level awareness programmes, promoting sustainable economic opportunities, integrating science with indigenous knowledge and practices, and strengthening rapid response teams. The interaction between indigenous status and ASC_{SQ} is negative and significant. Similarly, education level has a negative and significant effect. While age and monthly income do not have significant direct effects, their standard deviation estimates are significant (Table 4.3).

Table 4.3 Results of the CL, base RPL, and RPL interaction models.

Attributes and interactions	CL model	Base RPL model		RPL model with interactions	
	Coefficient	Coefficient	Std Dev	Coefficient	Std Dev
ASC _{SQ}	-0.674*** (0.196)	-11.284*** (2.412)	12.779*** (2.513)	-7.192*** (2.394)	9.690*** (1.953)
Awareness	0.335*** (0.095)	0.605*** (0.190)	0.650*** (0.205)	0.596*** (0.184)	0.484* (0.262)
Planning	-0.094 (0.103)	-0.117 (0.186)	0.078 (0.308)	-0.113 (0.183)	0.100 (0.425)
Diversify	0.042 (0.092)	0.184 (0.169)	0.504* (0.264)	0.172 (0.164)	0.632*** (0.238)
Sustainable	0.553*** (0.196)	0.900** (0.379)	1.532*** (0.334)	0.898** (0.371)	1.453*** (0.309)
Knowledge	0.307** (0.142)	0.651** (0.266)	0.175 (0.301)	0.631** (0.261)	0.147 (0.292)
Technology	0.132 (0.104)	0.250 (0.189)	0.334 (0.302)	0.242 (0.184)	0.346 (0.272)
Team	0.266*** (0.082)	0.592*** (0.170)	1.127*** (0.231)	0.583*** (0.167)	1.103*** (0.226)
Fund	-0.051 (0.112)	-0.066 (0.207)	0.747*** (0.261)	-0.058 (0.201)	0.644** (0.285)
Hour	-0.190*** (0.033)	-0.343*** (0.070)		-0.333*** (0.068)	
ASC_{SQ} × socio-demographic characteristics					
ASC _{SQ} × Age				0.910 (1.349)	9.384*** (2.208)
ASC _{SQ} × Gender				-1.209 (1.175)	0.341 (0.967)
ASC _{SQ} × Indigenous status				-3.945*** (1.505)	5.425*** (1.676)
ASC _{SQ} × Education level				-3.544*** (1.366)	4.808*** (1.327)
ASC _{SQ} × Monthly income				-0.993 (1.709)	4.963*** (1.140)
Model fit statistics					
No. of respondents	506	506		506	
No. of observations	1518	1518		1518	
No. of parameters	10	19		29	
Log Likelihood	-1481.312	-1165.680		-1158.850	
AIC	2982.6	2369.4		2375.7	
Pseudo R ²	0.045	0.301		0.305	

Notes: 1. ASC_{SQ} represents the alternative-specific constant associated with the status quo option. 2. Standard errors of the estimates are provided in parentheses. 3. *, **, and *** denote significance at 10%, 5%, and 1% levels.

4.4 Discussion

In this study, we examined how BZ residents in Chitwan NP navigate trade-offs between different human–wildlife coexistence strategies by using indicators of adaptive capacity as discrete choice experiment attributes. We found BZ residents prefer to learn to live with change and uncertainty, nurture diversity for reorganisation and renewal, combine different types of knowledge for learning, and create opportunities for self-organisation. We documented a negative and significant coefficient of the ASC_{SQ} , suggesting an absence of status quo bias among respondents (Table 4.3). This signifies that respondents do not prefer the existing scenario, characterised by inadequate skills to mitigate conflicts, limited economic opportunities at the grassroots level, insufficient skills to coexist with wildlife, and a limited ability to reorganise in the event of HWC. Rather than being driven by familiarity or resistance to change, respondents demonstrate a clear preference for improved scenarios that enhance their adaptive capacity, as cases of crop damages, human casualties (Ferdin et al., 2024b; Lamichhane et al., 2018) and wildlife fatalities² have been reported to be high in Chitwan NP. This absence of status quo bias aligns with previous studies (e.g., Barreiro-Hurle et al., 2018; Duijndam et al., 2020) with similar preferences for change, further underscoring the importance of adaptive coexistence strategies identified by the respondents.

4.4.1 Learning to live with change and uncertainty

The communities residing in the four administrative sectors of the park have diverse needs, and the intensity of conflicts also varies across these sectors due to the park and BZ's unique socio-ecological dynamics. Despite this diversity, across all communities, respondents clearly preferred targeted grassroots-level awareness programmes to increase community members' understanding of conflicts and the wildlife involved (Distefano, 2005). This preference likely reflects not only a desire for increased awareness but also a preference for community-controlled learning processes that build local capacity from within, rather than externally-imposed interventions.

In contrast, while effective land-use planning is considered a long-term solution to mitigate conflicts (Dunham et al., 2010; IUCN, 2023), it was not a preferred strategy by respondents of our study. This can be attributed to two primary factors: limited knowledge and experience regarding land-use planning and practices, and the development of distinct land-use management strategies by communities in different

² 341 wildlife fatalities due to human-wildlife conflict. Data regarding human-wildlife conflict incidents were compiled from Chitwan National Park annual reports for the fiscal years 2017 to 2023.

sectors based on their past experiences with wildlife. It is plausible that respondents perceive conservation priorities as superseding their own during the planning process, potentially leading to restrictions on current practices or even displacement due to the enforcement of land-use plans. Additionally, this rejection may reflect broader concerns about the planning process itself, where communities may associate land-use planning with loss of autonomy over their traditional lands and livelihoods, particularly given the historical context of conservation in Nepal where protected areas were often established with limited community consultation.

The human-modified agricultural landscape serves as a refuge habitat for wildlife from the park, while communities perceive it as land designated for agricultural use. Human settlements and agricultural lands, including areas for animal husbandry covers more than half of the BZ and represent the predominant land-use patterns in the areas where communities live (CNP, 2018). Notably, over 1,200 hectares of fringe land inside the Chitwan NP and BZ have been encroached (CNP, 2015). Residents in areas identified as encroachments may also be concerned that the enforcement of the land-use plan could necessitate their relocation. Although Nepal's land-use policy categorises land based on its suitability, its implementation has been inadequate on the ground (Chand, 2019). Furthermore, the park management recognises the challenges posed by poor enforcement of land-use regulations and the increasing pressure from human settlements in the BZ of Chitwan NP (CNP, 2018).

Although communities do not prefer land-use planning, it remains crucial for coexistence, especially with long-ranging species such as elephants and tigers. This presents an opportunity for the park management to identify and establish different zoning. By minimising overlap and reducing competition for resources and space between communities and wildlife, effective land-use planning can help lower negative interactions and promote coexistence within a shared landscape (Linnell et al., 2005). Enhanced engagement with communities and ensuring their meaningful participation are imperative for the successful implementation of such land-use planning initiatives.

Given the dynamic nature of HWCs, respondents' preference for grassroots-level awareness programmes reflects their need for community-controlled adaptation strategies that enhance their capacity to learn to live with change and uncertainty while maintaining agency in managing wildlife interactions.

4.4.2 Nurturing diversity for reorganisation and renewal

Indigenous communities such as the Bote, Majhi, Tharu, and Musahars of Chitwan NP have relied on the park's resources for centuries, including gathering wild fruits,

vegetables, and other non-timber forest products (Paudel et al., 2024). Underprivileged communities, including indigenous and Dalit groups, continue to face limited economic opportunities. They heavily rely on subsistence agriculture and forest resources to meet their livelihood needs (CNP, 2018; Lamichhane et al., 2018). This reliance results in frequent interactions with wildlife, making these communities the most affected by wildlife in Chitwan NP.

Our RPL model with interactions reveals important differences in preferences between indigenous and non-indigenous groups. The significant negative interaction between indigenous status and ASC_{SQ} indicates that indigenous respondents have a substantially stronger preference for moving away from the status quo compared to non-indigenous respondents. This finding aligns with the challenging circumstances indigenous communities face, as they bear disproportionate costs of HWCs while often receiving fewer benefits from conservation programmes (Coria & Calfucura, 2012). Their strong preference for alternatives to the status quo reflects an urgent desire for new strategies to human–wildlife coexistence that better address their specific needs and challenges. Similarly, education level shows a significant negative interaction with status quo, suggesting that higher educated respondents also strongly prefer alternatives to status quo.

Additionally, while age and monthly income do not exhibit significant mean effects in our model, both show strongly significant standard deviations, highlighting substantial heterogeneity in how these factors influence individual preferences. This indicates that the impacts of age and income on preferences are not uniform but rather vary considerably across respondents, potentially influenced by other socio-demographic characteristics or local circumstances. Such heterogeneity in preferences reflects the diverse socio-demographic context surrounding Chitwan NP, emphasising that effective human–wildlife coexistence strategies must be tailored to address the varying needs and circumstances of different community groups.

Our results suggest that respondents' strong preference for sustainable economic opportunities over diversifying partnerships reflects a desire for direct, tangible benefits that enhance community autonomy rather than creating dependencies on external partners. This preference for community-controlled economic development is particularly significant given the historical marginalisation of indigenous communities in conservation contexts. Rather than seeking external partnerships that may involve complex negotiations and potential loss of control, communities prefer sustainable economic strategies that they can directly implement and manage.

Although Chitwan NP attracts a multitude of tourists both locally and internationally, the tourism industry is heavily concentrated in the Eastern sector (Sauraha), whilst other sectors of the park remain underutilised. In this sector, more than half of the

households have been receiving the economic benefits from tourism (Spiteri & Nepal, 2008). This concentration of tourism in the Eastern sector leaves underprivileged communities in other sectors with fewer opportunities to find alternative livelihoods. Furthermore, indigenous fishing communities around Chitwan NP exemplify the persistent challenges in securing equitable access to natural resources and economic opportunities (Jana, 2007). Their struggles highlight the broader issue of socio-economic exclusion in protected areas, where policies and practices often prioritise wildlife protection and tourism over the livelihoods and rights of local communities. This may explain why promoting sustainable economic opportunities as a means of improving livelihoods was preferred by the respondents, particularly among indigenous communities whose strong preferences for change reflect their need for more equitable economic arrangements.

The BZ programme in Chitwan is supposed to reach all households, prioritising the most vulnerable ones. However, it has given higher priority to community infrastructure development and HWC mitigation measures (Lamichhane et al., 2019). Although these activities benefit all community members, measuring their impact at household level is difficult (Silwal et al., 2022). This could be the reason respondents prefer the sustainable economic opportunities through livelihood support and income generation programmes. A recent study from Chitwan documented 19% higher per capita household income in BZ compared to outside (Kandel et al., 2024).

However, the gap between those who benefit from the park and those who bear the costs of coexisting with wildlife poses significant obstacles to promoting coexistence in a place like Chitwan NP (Dunham et al., 2010). To address these gaps, Chitwan NP, in partnership with BZ committees and conservation organisations such as WWF's Terai Arc Landscape Programme, the Zoological Society of London, and the NTNC, has been implementing various livelihood enhancement and economic development initiatives. These programmes are designed to empower local communities, reduce their dependence on natural resources, and foster economic resilience, thereby supporting both community well-being and conservation objectives (NTNC, 2019; WWF, 2023; ZSL, 2023). Our findings suggest that these initiatives should pay particular attention to indigenous communities, whose strong preferences for alternative strategies indicate both their vulnerability and their readiness for more effective coexistence strategies.

Given these findings, residents' heavy reliance on agriculture and forest resources clearly increases their vulnerability to HWCs. Despite the challenging living conditions faced by indigenous and underprivileged groups, Chitwan NP should prioritise creating sustainable economic opportunities, a strategy supported by Digun-Aweto and van Eeden et al. (2021), who emphasise such opportunities for local communities living near protected areas. The preference for sustainable economic opportunities

thus represents both an endpoint goal (improved livelihoods) and a process preference (community-controlled development), underscoring the value of approaches that enhance both economic outcomes and community agency. This approach reinforces the importance of nurturing diversity for reorganisation and renewal, ultimately enhancing communities' adaptive capacity to coexist with wildlife.

4.4.3 Combining different types of knowledge for learning

Effectiveness of protected areas can improve by combining scientific knowledge and technologies with the indigenous knowledge (Distefano, 2005; Hussain et al., 2022). Respondents have shown strong support for integrating these methods, highlighting the importance of such integration. This support likely reflects both the value they place on their traditional knowledge and their preference for collaborative, participatory knowledge processes that respect local expertise. For instance, farmers in the Bia Biosphere Reserve in Ghana, Africa have requested that management acknowledge their traditional knowledge of forest and wildlife behaviour to aid in developing effective mitigation strategies (Nkansah-Dwamena, 2023). This situation is similar to that of the Bote communities in Chitwan NP, whose livelihoods have been alienated from their ancestral lands, leading to a decline in indigenous knowledge and creating a livelihood crisis (Rai & Dhakal, 2024). Despite the park management's efforts to employ their indigenous knowledge and recognise their role in collecting Gharial crocodile eggs and hatchlings, for example, Bote youths have little understanding of their traditional practices due to restrictions on engaging in their customary livelihoods (Rai & Dhakal, 2024).

Similarly, the Tharu, who once inhabited the land that is now Chitwan NP, were not consulted prior to the establishment of the park (Mahato, 2024). The relocated indigenous Tharu communities once used their indigenous knowledge to maintain streams flowing from the Chure hills, ensuring a steady water supply for agricultural lands. These areas have since been converted to grasslands, now serving as a major habitat for the park's wildlife (Mahato, 2024). Integrating the scientific and indigenous knowledge in mitigating conflicts complement each other in a coexistence landscape (IUCN, 2023). However, Rai and Dhakal (2024) further argue that the park's current management practices are insufficient to integrate indigenous knowledge and practices in Chitwan NP.

This highlights the challenges faced by indigenous communities, whose riverine livelihoods and diminishing knowledge of the land they have inhabited for centuries alongside iconic wildlife species are at risk. Other marginalised and underprivileged communities in Chitwan NP may encounter similar challenges, which has led respondents to prefer the integration of science with indigenous knowledge and

practices. On the other hand, information and communication technologies are also important tools for mitigating conflicts (Lewis et al., 2016). However, these technologies are only slowly gaining traction, as developing countries have yet to fully embrace them in fostering coexistence in places like Chitwan NP (Mwonzora & Mwonzora, 2024).

This preference for knowledge integration over technology-based solutions suggests that communities value approaches that build upon their existing knowledge systems rather than replacing them with external technological interventions. The preference for integrating scientific and indigenous knowledge thus represents both a desire for effective conservation solutions and a process preference for participatory approaches that validate and build upon local expertise rather than imposing external solutions.

4.4.4 Creating opportunities for self-organisation

Rapid response teams are first responders integral to HWC management. They are formed under the community-based anti-poaching unit in collaboration with members from BZ user committees and community forest user groups in Chitwan NP. In addition to monitoring poaching and combating illegal wildlife trade, they engage in rescuing injured, problematic, and orphaned wildlife and rehabilitating them. As first responders, they perform a wide range of tasks within the HWC context, including providing first aid, recovering the bodies of humans who have been killed, managing crowds, assisting communities in accessing relief payments, and raising public awareness (Barlow & Brooks, 2019; Wangdi, 2022). In the absence of these institutional arrangements, HWCs might surge to a level that reduces community tolerance. This decrease in tolerance could severely hinder conservation programmes and reverse the achievements made so far (Barlow & Brooks, 2019). These factors may explain why respondents preferred strengthening of rapid response teams. Additionally, such a preference was made over the establishment of a community fund in Chitwan NP. As the relief payment system is considered lengthy and time-consuming by local people (Ferdin et al., 2023; Lamichhane et al., 2019), this could be another significant factor.

Respondents' strong preference for strengthening rapid response teams over establishing community funds likely reflects both their recognition of the practical value of immediate response capacity and their preference for community-controlled organisational mechanisms. This preference pattern suggests that communities favour self-organisation approaches that enhance their direct capacity to respond to conflicts rather than external financial mechanisms that may involve complex bureaucratic processes.

Ensuring that local community members benefit from their involvement is crucial for maintaining their motivation and commitment in the long-run (Wangdi, 2022). While these teams provide significant value to both humans and wildlife, their members often face risks, financial constraints, and time limitations (Barlow & Brooks, 2019). While there are some instances of job creation by the Chitwan NP management, such as employing local people as park vehicle drivers, game scouts, kitchen staff, elephant mahouts, and workers in the Gharial Conservation and Breeding Centre (GCBC), the scale of these efforts remains limited. Expanding these initiatives could significantly enhance community involvement in conservation while providing much-needed economic incentives to BZ residents (personal communication with former chief of GCBC and a park assistant warden). This strategy would not only acknowledge their dedication but also strengthen the relationship between the park management and community members (Ferdin et al., 2024b). Recognising and consistently providing necessary training, resources, skill transfer, and incentives can motivate young individuals to participate, thereby reinforcing the effectiveness of the rapid response teams in Chitwan NP.

The preference for rapid response teams represents a desire for community agency in conflict management, the ability to act immediately when conflicts arise rather than depending on external assistance or navigating fund disbursement procedures. Rapid response teams are community-run initiatives that play a critical role in effectively responding to ongoing conflicts and facilitating communities' ability to cope with the aftermath of HWCs. Communities' clear preference for strengthening these teams underscores their importance as key mechanisms for creating opportunities for self-organisation. By enhancing local capacity to swiftly and effectively manage conflicts, these teams substantially strengthen residents' adaptive capacity, thus facilitating coexistence with wildlife.

4.4.5 Methodological considerations and future research directions

The non-market valuation method applied here is not only pertinent to our study's context but may also be valuable for other human-dominated landscapes where fostering human-wildlife coexistence is of paramount importance. For this reason, we now discuss some of the details of model performance that may provide insight for the application of these methods elsewhere: the log likelihood statistics indicate that the RPL model with interactions provides a better overall fit than both CL and RPL models. The significant standard deviations for several attributes confirm the presence of preference heterogeneity that would have been missed by simpler models such as CL (Birol et al., 2006). Our inclusion of the CL model confirmed the substantial improvement in explanatory power offered by RPL models. This further confirms that

respondents exhibited diverse preferences for coexistence strategies. The incorporation of interaction terms with socio-demographic characteristics further improved model fit and provided deeper insights into preference variation, particularly for indigenous communities and education levels.

However, there are a few limitations to consider: 1) discrete choice experiments are naturally restricted in their ability to include only a limited number of attributes and levels, which may have limited the complexity of the scenarios offered to the BZ residents; 2) as with all stated preference methods, there is potential for hypothetical bias. While our respondents appeared to understand the choice scenarios, their stated preferences might differ from actual behaviours if the proposed strategies were implemented.

Regarding respondents' understanding of choice experiment attributes, particularly "integrating science with indigenous knowledge and practices" required careful explanation during data collection. Enumerators were extensively trained to clarify complex concepts using concrete examples that respondents could relate to their daily experiences. For instance, when explaining the integration of scientific and traditional knowledge, enumerators used practical examples such as combining traditional visual deterrents (effigies and mannequins) with modern automated siren systems to create comprehensive wildlife alert and deterrent responses. Similarly, they explained how strategic defensive trench construction—a traditional practice—could be enhanced with electric fencing to more effectively prevent wildlife from entering settlements or agricultural fields. Despite these efforts, some respondents initially found it challenging to visualise what such integration would look like in practice, requiring additional clarification. Future studies should consider developing more detailed visual aids or conducting extended pilot testing to ensure all attributes are easily comprehensible to diverse community members.

Overall, the pilot testing prior to main survey with respondents helped ensure that the choice tasks were comprehensible to the BZ residents, increasing the reliability of our results. Additionally, our face-to-face interview approach with trained BZ enumerators helped minimise misunderstandings and non-responses, enhancing data quality. Before beginning the questionnaire, enumerators provided respondents with a clear explanation of the research topic. To guide choices and minimise cognitive burden, each choice set was accompanied by an illustration (Figure 4.2). Respondents were explicitly informed that all scenarios presented were hypothetical and did not reflect actual policy decisions. They were encouraged to ask questions before proceeding and during their decision-making process, allowing for informed choices with clear understanding. To ensure unbiased responses, enumerators instructed respondents not to discuss or be influenced by others during the choice-making process.

Moreover, HWCs are complex and site-specific, meaning that insights from this study may not be directly applicable to other protected areas seeking to facilitate coexistence. Nevertheless, future studies within Chitwan NP may benefit from: 1) focusing on BZ resident preferences regarding specific species, such as deer and rhinoceros, which are primarily responsible for crop raiding; 2) a transboundary comparative study of Tharu community preferences for coexistence between Chitwan NP and India's adjoining Valmiki Tiger Reserve could yield significant insights to enhance transboundary conservation efforts.

4.5 Conclusions and recommendations

Our findings reveal considerable preference heterogeneity amongst BZ residents regarding human–wildlife coexistence strategies, with indigenous and educated individuals showing strong preferences for organising grassroots-level awareness programmes, promoting sustainable economic opportunities, integrating science with indigenous knowledge, and strengthening rapid response teams. This heterogeneity underscores a critical insight: effective conservation strategies cannot follow a one-size-fits-all approach but must be tailored to diverse community needs and circumstances. Importantly, our results suggest that community preferences reflect not only desired conservation outcomes but also preferences for participatory, community-controlled processes that enhance local autonomy in wildlife management. As wildlife increasingly adapts to human presence in Chitwan NP, enhancing local communities' adaptive capacity through targeted, preference-informed interventions becomes essential for facilitating coexistence. By combining adaptive capacity indicators with discrete choice experiments, this study provides a replicable framework for developing community-centred co-adaptation strategies in human-dominated landscapes across Nepal and similar contexts globally.

The research points to the following actionable recommendations: 1) develop livelihood programmes that prioritise indigenous communities by leveraging their traditional art, culture, and heritage; 2) link these cultural assets with ecotourism to create sustainable income streams while preserving cultural identity; 3) combine scientific methods with indigenous knowledge to develop effective and context-sensitive coexistence strategies; 4) establish and mobilise well-equipped and trained rapid response teams to address HWCs efficiently, particularly in BZ; 5) continue awareness-raising initiatives targeting all communities and stakeholders to foster understanding, empathy, and collaboration in coexistence efforts.

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Author contributions

Arockia E J Ferdin: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft (Lead), Visualization (Figure 4.2, All Tables), Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. Abhinaya Pathak: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. Mahirah Kamaludin: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation. Babu Ram Lamichhane: Writing – review & editing, Visualization (Figure 4.1), Writing – original draft. Shyam Kumar Shah: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. Udit Chandra Aryal: Writing – review & editing, Project administration. Nagarajan Baskaran: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision

5 Synthesis

5.1 Introduction

This thesis set out to explore community-preferred coexistence strategies and gain insight into local communities' perceptions of the importance and effectiveness of HWC management strategies in Chitwan NP, Nepal. Drawing on two empirical chapters conducted in the park's buffer zone, presented in Chapters 3 and 4, this chapter synthesizes the key findings, identifies cross-cutting themes of direct relevance to the park management, and offers integrated recommendations for advancing workable coexistence in Chitwan NP. Figure 5.1 presents the conceptual framework underpinning this thesis, illustrating how community preferences examined through a DCE and community perceptions assessed through IPA jointly inform HWC management strategies to achieve co-adaptation and workable coexistence in Chitwan NP.

Chitwan NP's conservation achievements over the past five decades are considerable. The recovery of the greater one-horned rhinoceros, Royal Bengal tiger, Asian elephant, and other wildlife from the brink of extinction stands as a testament to the effectiveness of Nepal's conservation triangle model. Yet this very success has intensified the challenges facing buffer zone communities, as wildlife increasingly ventures into human-dominated agricultural landscapes, resulting in escalating crop damage, livestock depredation, property destruction, and human casualties that also lead to wildlife casualties. Addressing these challenges demands more than well-intentioned programmes and requires management strategies that are grounded in what communities actually need, value, and prefer.

5.2 Synthesis of key findings

5.2.1 Communities are dissatisfied with the current situation and are ready for change

Chapter 3 found that all eight HWC management strategies evaluated showed significant gaps between their perceived importance and actual performance, meaning that across every area assessed, the park management is falling short of what communities expect and need. This is not a minor dissatisfaction, as all strategies, regardless of type, are underperforming relative to how important communities

consider them to be, for both farmers and non-farmers alike. Chapter 4 independently corroborates this, confirming that buffer zone residents do not prefer the existing situation and actively desire change. This finding should be read as an opportunity, not a criticism.

5.2.2 Livelihoods and economic security are the foundation of coexistence

Both chapters independently and consistently identified livelihood-related interventions as the highest priority for communities. In Chapter 3, enhanced livelihood diversification skills, promotion of alternative livelihoods, and fast-tracked compensation schemes emerged as the three high-priority strategies, critically important to communities yet among the poorest-performing areas of the park management. In Chapter 4, promoting sustainable economic opportunities was the most strongly preferred strategy overall, particularly among indigenous communities who bear disproportionate costs from HWC while receiving fewer conservation benefits. This suggests that economic security is not a supplementary concern but rather the foundational condition upon which coexistence must be built.

5.2.3 Awareness and community engagement are working — but need to evolve

Chapter 3 found that resource security and awareness strategies are the two areas where the park management is performing well. Chapter 4 reinforces the value of awareness, with grassroots-level awareness programmes identified as the most preferred strategy for helping communities learn to live with change and uncertainty. However, an important nuance emerges from Chapter 4: communities do not simply want information delivered to them from the top down. They prefer community-controlled learning processes that build adaptive capacity from within, in which they are active participants rather than passive recipients. This signals that the park's awareness programmes, while effective, have room to evolve into more participatory, community-led platforms.

5.2.4 Rapid response teams matter more than their IPA ranking suggests

In Chapter 3, communities ranked strengthening RRTs as a lower priority compared to livelihood and compensation strategies. However, Chapter 4 reveals a different picture: when communities are asked to actively choose between coexistence strategies, strengthening RRTs is strongly and consistently preferred as a mechanism for self-

organisation and immediate conflict response. Communities may not rank RRTs as urgently important compared to livelihood needs, but when given genuine agency to shape their coexistence future, they consistently favour community-led, immediate-response mechanisms over more bureaucratic alternatives such as community funds. RRTs represent communities' desire for agency and capacity, and this should not be underestimated by the park management.

5.2.5 Sector-specific variation demands tailored management

Both chapters consistently found that communities across Chitwan NP's four administrative sectors, namely Kasara, Sauraha, Madi, and Amaltari, do not experience or respond to HWC uniformly. Chapter 3 showed significant differences in perceived importance and performance of strategies across sectors, with Kasara and Madi emerging as particularly vulnerable and underserved relative to the Eastern sector of Sauraha, where tourism concentration has brought greater economic benefits. Chapter 4 further showed that indigenous communities and educated individuals have a substantially stronger preference for moving away from the status quo. Together, these findings make a strong case against uniform, park-wide blanket strategies and in favour of sector-specific approaches that reflect the distinct socio-ecological and demographic realities of each sector.

5.2.6 Indigenous communities require dedicated attention

A thread running through both chapters is the vulnerability and distinctiveness of indigenous communities in relation to HWC. These communities bear disproportionate costs of coexistence due to their heavy reliance on subsistence agriculture and forest resources, their historical alienation from the park lands, and the erosion of indigenous ecological knowledge that once supported sustainable resource use. Chapter 4's finding that indigenous respondents have the strongest preference for alternatives to the status quo, and that they particularly value the integration of scientific and indigenous knowledge, reflects both their urgency and their readiness for more equitable management approaches. Their traditional knowledge systems, if recognised, respected, and incorporated into the park's management, represent an underutilised resource that could meaningfully enhance coexistence outcomes across the park.

5.3 Implications for the park management and conservation policy

The findings of this thesis carry three broader implications for how the park management approaches the challenge of HWC.

First, community preferences are not supplementary data but foundational inputs for effective management. Both chapters demonstrate that communities in Chitwan NP hold clear, coherent, and context-specific views about what they need from HWC management. Where the park management falls short of these expectations, as is the case with livelihood, compensation, and skills development, the social legitimacy that underpins long-term conservation success is quietly eroded. Listening to and acting on community preferences is not simply good practice; it is a prerequisite for durable coexistence.

Second, adaptive capacity should be explicitly incorporated into the park's management framework. Chapter 4 demonstrates that communities are not passive recipients of management interventions but active agents with the willingness and capacity to adapt to the presence of wildlife in their surroundings. Management that invests in communities' adaptive capacity, through livelihood diversification, knowledge integration, and self-organisation, is more likely to achieve durable coexistence than management that focuses narrowly on reactive conflict mitigation after incidents have occurred.

Third, the conservation triangle model that underpins the park's management philosophy, uniting the park management, the Nepalese Army, and local communities, can only fulfil its potential when the community side of that triangle is genuinely empowered, economically secure, and meaningfully heard. The findings of this thesis suggest that the community pillar of this model, while valued in principle, requires greater investment and more consistent attention in practice, particularly in sectors and among demographic groups that have historically been underserved.

5.4 Integrated recommendations for the park management

5.4.1 Elevate livelihood security as the centrepiece of HWC management strategy

The convergent finding across both chapters, that livelihood diversification, sustainable economic opportunities, and fast-tracked compensation are simultaneously the most important and most underperforming areas of HWC management, demands a clear and urgent policy response. These interventions must

be elevated from supplementary buffer zone activities to central, adequately resourced pillars of the park's HWC strategy. This is especially urgent in the Kasara and Madi sectors, where economic vulnerability and conflict exposure are highest and where tourism-driven income opportunities remain limited. Livelihood programmes should be explicitly designed to reach the most vulnerable households, with dedicated provisions for indigenous communities that leverage traditional knowledge, cultural assets, and heritage as livelihood foundations rather than treating them as obstacles to conservation.

5.4.2 Develop sector-specific HWC management sub-plans

Given the consistent evidence of significant variation in community needs, HWC exposure, and management performance across the park's four sectors, a single park-wide management approach is insufficient. The park management should develop targeted HWC management sub-plans for each of the four administrative sectors, through meaningful participatory processes with respective BZUCs, community representatives, and indigenous community leaders. These sub-plans should reflect sector-specific wildlife interactions, livelihoods and their needs, and management priorities, and should be reviewed and updated on a regular cycle in consultation with communities.

5.4.3 Evolve awareness programmes into community-led adaptive learning platforms

The park's awareness programmes are among the few areas where community satisfaction is high, and this foundation should be continued and built upon. However, both chapters indicate that communities want to move beyond one-way information delivery toward participatory processes in which they are active agents of learning. The park management should work toward transitioning awareness programmes into grassroots-level, community-controlled learning platforms, integrating scientific knowledge with indigenous ecological knowledge, equipping communities with practical skills to understand and respond to wildlife behaviour, and creating spaces for community members to share their own experiences and strategies across sectors and BZUCs.

5.4.4 Strengthen and formally recognise rapid response teams

The strong preference expressed by communities for strengthening RRTs, above even the establishment of community funds, signals that these teams represent far more than a logistical mechanism. They embody communities' desire for agency, self-

organisation, and immediate capacity to manage conflict at the local level. The park management should prioritise the expansion, training, equipment, and formal recognition of RRT members. This includes establishing appropriate incentive structures, creating pathways for RRT involvement in park employment, and ensuring that teams in all four sectors, not just those closest to park headquarters, are adequately resourced. Investing in RRTs is investing in community trust and conservation legitimacy simultaneously.

5.4.5 Integrate indigenous knowledge into formal management processes

The preference for integrating scientific and indigenous knowledge, expressed most strongly by indigenous respondents, points to an underutilised opportunity for the park management. Indigenous communities possess deep ecological knowledge of the landscape, wildlife behaviour, and resource management practices accumulated over generations. The park management, in partnership with BZUCs and relevant conservation organisations, should develop formal mechanisms for incorporating this knowledge into HWC management planning, species-specific mitigation strategies, and community-based conservation activities. This not only enhances management effectiveness but also strengthens the cultural dignity and conservation engagement of indigenous communities.

5.4.6 Institutionalise community feedback as a regular management tool

Chapter 3 demonstrated that a structured, community-based assessment of management importance and performance can be conducted efficiently and at relatively low cost across the park's buffer zone. The park management should consider institutionalising a regular community feedback exercise, conducted every two to three years in coordination with BZUCs, as a practical tool for tracking whether management performance is keeping pace with community expectations over time. This would create a systematic feedback loop that enables adaptive management responses to changing community needs, rather than relying on ad hoc consultation or crisis-driven adjustments.

5.5 Conclusion

Achieving workable coexistence in Chitwan NP requires management strategies that communities consider important, that are perceived to be performing well, and that align with communities' ability to coexist with wildlife. The human-modified

agricultural landscape surrounding the park is home to tens of thousands of people who live alongside, and largely tolerate, some of the world's most iconic wildlife. Sustaining the park's remarkable conservation achievements over the long term depends on that tolerance, and earning and maintaining it requires management that is responsive, equitable, and genuinely attentive to community needs. Recognising and investing in communities not simply as beneficiaries of conservation but as genuine partners in the conservation triangle model is the most effective long-term strategy available to the park management.

Figure 5.1 Conceptual model for operationalizing workable human-wildlife coexistence

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Appendix

Appendix 1.1: Research permission from Department of National Parks and Wildlife Conservation, Nepal

पत्र संख्या : ४३१/०७८/७९
चलानी नं. : ५६२ इको

नेपाल सरकार
वन तथा वातावरण मन्त्रालय
राष्ट्रिय निकुञ्ज तथा वन्यजन्तु संरक्षण विभाग

(..... शाखा)

नेपाल सरकार
वन तथा वातावरण मन्त्रालय
राष्ट्रिय निकुञ्ज तथा वन्यजन्तु संरक्षण विभाग
बबरमहन, काठमाडौं
२०३१

फोन नं. : ४२२०८३०
: ४२२०९१२
: ४२२०९२६
फ्याक्स नं. : ४२२७६७५

पो.ब. नं. - ८६०
बबरमहन, काठमाडौं
Email : info@dnwpc.gov.np
http://www.dnwpc.gov.np

मिति: २०७८/०९/२८

विषय: अध्ययन अनुमति सम्बन्धमा ।

श्री चितवन राष्ट्रिय निकुञ्ज कार्यालय, कसरा, चितवन ।

प्रस्तुत विषयमा National Dong Hwa University, Taiwan का PhD विद्यार्थी Mr. Arockia EJ Ferdin ले “Establishing an Evaluation Framework for endangered and vulnerable species in Chitwan National Park” विषयमा Choice experiment and importance performance analysis, Stakeholder and Face to Face Interviews with household in buffer zone of Chitwan National Park लगायतका विधिहरू प्रयोग गरी जनवरी २०२२ देखि ३१ जुलाई २०२२ सम्म अध्ययन अनुसन्धान गर्ने प्रस्ताव उपर आवश्यक कारवाही हुँदा वन तथा वातावरण मन्त्रालयको च.नं. ४७३, मिति २०७८/०९/२८ गतेको पत्र बमोजिम तपसिलमा उल्लेखित शर्तहरूको परिधि भित्र रही अध्ययन अनुसन्धान अनुमति प्रदान गर्ने वन तथा वातावरण मन्त्रालय (सचिक्स्तर) बाट मिति २०७८/०९/२६ मा निर्णय भएको व्यहोरा निर्णयानुसार अनुरोध छ ।

शर्तहरू :

१. अनुसन्धानकर्ताले राष्ट्रिय निकुञ्ज तथा वन्यजन्तु संरक्षण ऐन, २०२९ र नियमावली, २०३० तथा मातहतका सबै नियमावलीहरूको पूर्ण रूपमा पालना गर्नु पर्नेछ ।
२. अध्ययन गर्दा सम्बन्धित संरक्षित क्षेत्र कार्यालयसंग समन्वय गरी कार्यालयमा कार्यरत कर्मचारीको रोहबरमा गर्नु पर्नेछ ।
३. अनुसन्धानकर्ताले आफ्नो अनुसन्धानको प्रस्ताव सम्बन्धित संरक्षित क्षेत्र कार्यालयमा समेत पेश गर्नु पर्नेछ ।
४. अनुसन्धानकर्ताले अनुसन्धान समाप्त भएपछि एक प्रति कागजी प्रतिवेदन र एक प्रति इलेक्ट्रोनिक प्रतिवेदन यस विभाग र सम्बन्धित संरक्षित क्षेत्र कार्यालयमा बुझाउनु पर्नेछ ।
५. अनुसन्धानकर्ताले नतिजाहरू प्रकाशित गर्दा अनुसन्धानमा संलग्न यस विभाग र अन्तरगतका कर्मचारीको योगदानको आधारमा सहलेखकको रूपमा समावेश गराउनु पर्नेछ ।
६. कुनै पनि नमुना संकलन गर्न पाइने छैन ।
७. तोकिएका शर्तहरूको पालना नगरेमा विभागले कुनै पनि समयमा अनुमतिपत्र रद्द गर्न सक्नेछ ।
८. बाँकीको हकमा प्रचलित कानून बमोजिम हुनेछ ।

वेद कुमार ढकाल
इकोलोजिष्ट

बोधार्थ:
Mr. Arockia EJ Ferdin : सम्बन्धित संरक्षण क्षेत्र कार्यालयसंग समन्वय गरी अध्ययन अनुसन्धान गर्नु हुन ।

Appendix 1.2: Research permission from the Chitwan National Park Headquarters, Kasara

नेपाल सरकार
वन तथा वातावरण मन्त्रालय
राष्ट्रिय निकुञ्ज तथा वन्यजन्तु संरक्षण विभाग
चितवन राष्ट्रिय निकुञ्ज कार्यालय

पत्र संख्या:- ०७८/७९
चलानी नं.:- २००३

मिति: २०७८।०९।३०

विषय : अध्ययन अनुमति सम्बन्धमा ।

Mr. Arockia E J Ferdin,
National Dong Hwa University, Taiwan
(ferdin@posteo.net)

प्रस्तुत विषयमा श्री राष्ट्रिय निकुञ्ज तथा वन्यजन्तु संरक्षण विभाग, बबरमहल, काठमाण्डौको च.नं. ९७२ (०७८/०७९ इको) मिति २०७८।०९।२८ को पत्रानुसार तपाईंलाई यस चितवन राष्ट्रिय निकुञ्जको मध्यवर्ती क्षेत्रमा " Establishing an Evaluation Framework for endangered and vulnerable species in Chitwan National Park " विषयमा Choice experiment and Importance performance analysis, Stakeholders and Face to Face Interviews with household in Buffer zone of Chitwan National Park लगायतका विधिहरु प्रयोग गरी अध्ययन अनुसन्धान गर्न January, 2022 देखि July 31, 2022 सम्मका लागि राष्ट्रिय निकुञ्ज तथा वन्यजन्तु संरक्षण ऐन २०२९, चितवन राष्ट्रिय निकुञ्ज नियमावली २०३० र तपसिलका शर्तहरुको अधिनमा रही सम्बन्धित सेक्टर कार्यालय, रेञ्जपोष्ट, पोष्ट तथा यस कार्यालयले तोकेको व्यक्ति संगको समन्वय एवं निर्देशनमा अध्ययन अनुसन्धान गर्न अनुमति दिइएको ब्यहोरा अनुरोध छ ।

तपसिल

१. अनुसन्धानकर्ताले राष्ट्रिय निकुञ्ज तथा वन्यजन्तु संरक्षण ऐन २०२९, नियमावली २०३०, चि.रा.नि नियमावली २०३० तथा यस मातहतका सबै नियमावलीहरुको पूर्ण रुपमा पालना गर्नुपर्नेछ ।
२. अनुसन्धान कार्य गर्दा, गराउंदा यस कार्यालय तथा नजिकको सेक्टर, पोष्टसंग अनिवार्य रुपमा समन्वय गरी कार्यालयमा कार्यरत कर्मचारीको रोहबरमा गर्नु पर्नेछ ।
३. अनुसन्धाकर्ताले आफ्नो अनुसन्धानको प्रस्ताव यस कार्यालयमा पेश गर्नुपर्नेछ ।
४. अनुसन्धान समाप्त भएपछि सो को एकप्रति कागजी प्रतिवेदन र एकप्रति **Electronic र Hardcopy** यस कार्यालयमा अनिवार्य रुपमा बुझाउनुपर्नेछ ।
५. अनुसन्धानकर्ताले नतिजाहरु प्रकाशित गर्दा अनुसन्धानमा संलग्न कर्मचारीको योगदानको आधारमा सह-लेखकको रुपमा समावेश गराउनु पर्नेछ ।
६. अनुसन्धानको क्रममा अनुसन्धानसंग सम्बन्धित कुनै पनि नमूनाहरु संकलन गर्न पाइने छैन ।
७. उक्त कार्य सुर्यादय पूर्व र सुर्यास्त पछि गर्न पाइने छैन ।
८. वन र वन्यजन्तुलाई कुनै पनि प्रकारले हानी नोक्सानी गर्न पाइने छैन ।
९. तोकिएको शर्तहरुको पालना नगरेमा कार्यालयले कुनैपनि समयमा अनुमति पत्र रद्द गर्न सक्नेछ ।
१०. अनुसन्धानमा सहभागिहरु: सहजकर्ता- उदित चन्द्र अर्याल (९८६७७९९८६)

(राजू धिमिरे)
नि. प्रमुख संरक्षण अधिकृत

बोधार्थ
श्री खड्गदल गण, कसरा व्यारेक, चितवन : जानकारीको लागि अनुरोध छ ।
श्री सौराहा/अमलटारी/कसरा/बगईमाडी सेक्टर : जानकारी तथा आवश्यक सहयोग तथा अनुगमन गर्नुहुन अनुरोध छ ।

ईमेल : info@chitwannationalpark.gov.np , वेब: www.chitwannationalpark.gov.np

Appendix 2: Fieldwork pictures

Fieldwork activities showing enumerators conducting household surveys with buffer zone residents across diverse community settings in Chitwan National Park

a. Entrance gate at Chitwan National Park, b. Mustard field and settlement in Mrigakunja buffer zone of Chitwan National Park., c. A majestic greater one-horned rhino walks on the road in Chitwan National Park, d. Chitwan National Park Headquarters, Kasara, Chitwan

Appendix 3: Survey Questionnaire — Chapter 3

Date: _____ BZUC: _____ No: _____

District Name: _____ Name of the Sector: _____

Part 1: Resident's experience and their wildlife encounters

1. Do you or your family encounter any conflicts with wildlife in the past five years? Yes No
 - a) If **yes**, what damage? (1) Human casualty (2) Human injury (3) Livestock casualty (4) Livestock injury (5) Crop damage (6) Property damage (7) Others, _____
 - b) If **yes**, which wild species? (1) Elephant (2) Tiger (3) Rhinoceros (4) Deer (5) Leopard (6) Wild boar (7) Monkey (8) Crocodile (9) Gaur (10) Others, _____
2. Have you applied compensation for the above mentioned losses? Yes No
 - a) If **yes**, any compensation is received for the above-mentioned losses? Yes No
 - b) If **yes**, are you satisfied with the compensation received for the losses? Yes No
3. Do you think getting compensated for losses is a lengthy process?
 - (1) Strongly Disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly Agree
4. Do you think HWC is increasing in recent years?
 - (1) Strongly Disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly Agree
5. Do you think building fences are an effective way to reduce HWC?
 - (1) Strongly Disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly Agree
6. Do you think that compensation is an effective way to reduce suffering due to HWC? Yes No

Part 2: Residents' perceived importance and performance on strategies

Degree of Importance					HWC management strategies	Degree of performance				
SU	U	N	I	SI		SD	D	N	A	SA
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enhanced livelihood diversification skills	<input type="checkbox"/>								
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ability to secure resources	<input type="checkbox"/>								
<input type="checkbox"/>	Strengthen HWC awareness workshops	<input type="checkbox"/>								
<input type="checkbox"/>	Cultivation of buffer crops	<input type="checkbox"/>								
<input type="checkbox"/>	Fast-tracked compensation scheme	<input type="checkbox"/>								
<input type="checkbox"/>	Promotion of alternative livelihoods	<input type="checkbox"/>								
<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve park-people relationship	<input type="checkbox"/>								
<input type="checkbox"/>	Strengthening of rapid response teams	<input type="checkbox"/>								

Part 3: Socio-demographic data

1. Gender: Male Female
2. Religion: (1) Hinduism (2) Buddhism (3) Kiratism (4) Christianity (5) Islam
(6) Others, _____
3. What is your cast & ethnicity: _____
4. Indigenous community: Yes No
5. Marital status: (1) Single (2) Married (3) Divorced (4) Widowed
6. Age: (1) 20-29 y/o (2) 30-39 y/o (3) 40-49 y/o (4) 50-59 y/o (5) > 60 y/o
7. Education level: (1) Didn't attend school (2) Primary school (3) Middle school
(4) High school (5) Higher Secondary School (6) Diploma
(7) Undergraduate (8) Graduate & higher
8. Occupation: (1) Farmer (2) Fisherman (3) Daily wager (4) Tour guide
(5) Forest guard (6) Private business (7) Others, _____
9. Monthly income: (1) ≤ NPR10,000 (2) NPR 10,001-15,000 (3) NPR 15,001-20,000
(4) NPR 20,001-25,000 (5) NPR 25,001-30,000 (6) > NPR 30,001
10. What is the main source of family income:
(1) Farming (2) Fishing (3) Daily wages (4) Tour guide (5) Forest guard
(6) Foreign remittance (7) Private business (8) Others, _____
11. Family size: (1) ≤3 members (2) 4-6 members (3) 7-9 members (4) ≥10 members
12. How many years has your family been living in this village:
(1) ≤15 years (2) 16-30 years (3) 31-45 years (4) 46-50 years (5) ≥60 years

Your contribution to this research is highly appreciated. We understand that your time is valuable, and we thank you for providing us with your honest opinions and perspectives.

Appendix 4: Survey Questionnaire — Chapter 4

Date: _____ BZUC: _____ No: _____

District Name: _____ Name of the Sector: _____

Part 1: Resident’s attitude and awareness on wildlife

- Do you agree that living in harmony with nature will benefit you and the threatened species?
 (1) Strongly Disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly Agree
- How concerned are you about species extinction?
 (1) Not at all concerned (2) Slightly concerned (3) Moderately concerned (4) Very concerned
 (5) Extremely concerned
- What do you think is the major cause of species extinction? (Multiple choice)
 (1) Human over-population (2) Agricultural expansion (3) Retaliatory killing
 (4) Habitat loss (5) Climate change (6) Illegal poaching (7) Not sure
- Do you think humans are speeding the species extinction rate?
 (1) Strongly Disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly Agree
- Do you think threatened species deserve a chance to thrive and protected?
 (1) Strongly Disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly Agree
- Are you a part of any wildlife conservation organization? Yes No

Part 2: Choice tasks

CHOICE SET 1			
	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Status Quo
Learning to live with change and uncertainty	Inadequate skills to mitigate HWC 	Organize grass-root level awareness programs 	Inadequate skills to mitigate HWC
Nurturing diversity for reorganization and renewal	Limited economic opportunities at grassroots level 	Diversify partners & cooperation to enhance economic opportunities 	Limited economic opportunities at grassroots level
Combining different types of knowledge for learning	Combine ICTs with local information sharing system 	Combine ICTs with local information sharing system 	Inadequate skills to coexist with wildlife

Creating opportunity for self-organization	Strengthen rapid response teams 		
Willingness to Participate	3 hour / week	10 hour / week	0 hour / week
Please Tick	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

CHOICE SET 2			
	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Status Quo
Learning to live with change and uncertainty	Incorporate land use planning in coping strategies 		
Nurturing diversity for reorganization and renewal	Diversify partners & cooperation to enhance economic opportunities 		
Combining different types of knowledge for learning	Combine ICTs with local information sharing system 		
Creating opportunity for self-organization	Establish community fund 		
Willingness to Participate	7 hour / week	7 hour / week	0 hour / week
Please Tick	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

CHOICE SET 3			
	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Status Quo
Learning to live with change and uncertainty	Organize grass-root level awareness programs 		
Nurturing diversity for reorganization and renewal	Diversify partners & cooperation to enhance economic opportunities 		
Combining different types of knowledge for learning	Inadequate skills to coexist with wildlife 		
Creating opportunity for self-organization	Strengthen rapid response teams 		
Willingness to Participate	7 hour / week	10 hour / week	0 hour / week
Please Tick	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Part 3: Socio-demographic data

1. Gender: Male Female
2. Religion: (1) Hinduism (2) Buddhism (3) Christianity (4) Islam
(5) Others, _____
3. Indigenous community: Yes No (Caste: _____)
4. Settlement type: (1) Urban (2) Rural
5. Marital status: (1) Single (2) Married (3) Divorced (4) Widowed
6. Age: (1) 20-29 y/o (2) 30-39 y/o (3) 40-49 y/o (4) 50-59 y/o (5) > 60 y/o
7. Education level: (1) Didn't attend school (2) Primary school (3) Middle school
(4) High school (5) Higher Secondary School (6) Diploma
(7) Undergraduate (8) Graduate & higher
8. Occupation: (1) Farmer (2) Fisherman (3) Daily wager (4) Private business
(5) Office employee (6) Others, _____
9. Monthly income: (1) ≤ NPR10,000 (2) NPR 10,001-15,000 (3) NPR 15,001-20,000
(4) NPR 20,001-25,000 (5) NPR 25,001-30,000 (6) > NPR 30,001
10. Family size: (1) ≤3 members (2) 4-6 members (3) 7-9 members (4) ≥10 members

Your contribution to this research is highly appreciated. We understand that your time is valuable, and we thank you for providing us with your honest opinions and perspectives.

Appendix 5: List of publications

Publications arising from this research:

1. **Ferdin, A. E. J.**, Aryal, U.C., Dhungana, N., Lamichhane, B.R., Chook, J.W., & Lee, C.H. (2024). Prioritizing human-wildlife conflict management strategies through importance-performance analysis: Insights from Chitwan National Park, Nepal. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 126675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2024.126675>
2. **Ferdin, A. E. J.**, Pathak, A., Kamaludin, M., Lamichhane, B.R., Shayam, K.S., Aryal, U.C., & Baskaran, N. (2025). Understanding residents' preferences for adaptive capacity in human-wildlife coexistence: a case study from Nepal's biodiversity hotspot. *European Journal of Wildlife Research*, 71(5). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10344-025-01963-y>

Related publications by the author:

1. **Ferdin, A. E. J.**, Lee, C.H., Dhungana, N., Chook, J.W., Baskaran, N., & Pathak, A. (2023). Eliciting community-preferred policy alternatives for achieving workable coexistence in a human-dominated landscape: Insights from Chitwan National Park, Nepal. *Conservation Science and Practice*, 5(11), e13026. <https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.13026>
2. **Ferdin, A. E. J.**, Pandey, R., Shayam, K.S., Aryal, U.C., Paudel, K., Pathak, A., Zangmo, R., Lamichhane, B.R., Abas, A., & Baskaran, N. (2026). Importance of context-specific community perspectives in human-wildlife coexistence: Evidence from Chitwan National Park, Nepal. *Conservation Science and Practice*, 8(4), e70245. <https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.70245>

Curriculum vitae

Arockia E J Ferdin was born on 8 June 1990 in Theni, Tamil Nadu, India. He completed his Bachelor of Engineering in Electronics and Communication Engineering at Jeppiaar Engineering College, Chennai, in 2012. He then pursued an M.Tech in Nanotechnology at Sathyabama University, Chennai, graduating in 2015. During his M.Tech, he developed a keen interest in environmental studies and sustainable development. Following his M.Tech, he worked as a Project Associate at the National Center for Nanoscience and Technology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China, from 2015 to 2017. Motivated by a growing passion for ecology and conservation, Ferdin enrolled in an M.Sc. in Ecology and Environment Studies at Nalanda University, Rajgir, India, completing it in 2019 with a thesis on unlocking the potential of ecotourism in Rajgir. He subsequently joined the Ph.D. programme in Natural Resources and Environmental Studies at National Dong Hwa University, Hualien, Taiwan, from 2021 to 2024. Beyond his research interests in human–wildlife interactions, he has developed an interest in wildlife–plastic interactions and plastic waste management. He actively engages in science communication through platforms such as *Current Conservation*, his personal website, and Research Communities by Springer Nature. In 2025, Ferdin joined the Center for Research in Development, Social and Environment (SEEDS), Faculty of Social Sciences & Humanities, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (The National University of Malaysia) as a Postdoctoral Researcher. He is currently leading a project on human–elephant interactions in Sabah, Malaysia. He is a member of the Society for Conservation Biology and has served as a peer reviewer for more than 20 international journals. Beyond academia, he has been actively involved in environmental volunteerism with DOMI Earth and Greenpeace Taiwan, and co-founded the A World Project, which facilitated cultural exchange between Taiwanese indigenous communities and school students. He is also an active advocate for a zero waste lifestyle.

